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“Revolut Ltd Establishment as Revolut Bank UAB, Growth and Analysis of Comparative and Common Size Financial Statements”

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Abbreviations:

SUSB: Statistics of US Firms

EU: European Union

SBA: Small Business Administration

European Union (EU)

European Court of Justice (ECJ)

United States of America (USA)

Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB)

ROE: Return on Equity

ROA: Return on Assets

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Abstract:

With the advent of digital transformation, business models and retail financial services have been reimagined. One notable result of this transition is the creation of "challenger Banks" a type of financial innovation. Challenger banks include both digital-native banks and fintech firms that operate primarily through digital technology and pose a threat to existing, large-scale banks. These forward-thinking financial service firms consider agility and the use of new technologies as essential success factors. Due to their branchless and mobile-centric operations, Challenger banks focus on delivering superior user experiences and competitive pricing for certain financial services.

Revolut Ltd. is one of the challenger banks among them, which was incorporated on 6th December 2013 and registered as a bank fully on 13th Dec 2021, specializing in money transfer and currency conversion services. It also provides services such as peer-to-peer payments, Savings Vaults, multiple accounts, and holiday booking possibilities.

The growth of the Bank is easily visible in the form of its positive income over three years, strengths like the user-friendly app, and an increase in the number of customers from 0.1 million in the year 2016 to 30 million by the year June 2023, even though it passed through some negative consequences.

As a new upcoming challenger bank, its earnings are higher the maximum amount is used for operational expenses which triggers a decline in the consolidated income of the bank. In comparison with another fintech bank like Monzo Bank. Revolut Bank UAB can boost its income as well as its customers. As a fintech bank, it doesn't have physical branches, but it has escalated in growth very early. Traditional banks like Commerzbank, existing for many decades are also planning and executing to close down most of the branches and operate digitally to save cost and use it fruitfully.

The profitability of the bank is less as compared to Commerzbank, but there is growth in profit in fluctuating mode from high-profit earner to low decline in profit and then again increase in profit.

Keywords: Fintech, Mobile centric operations, digital-native banks and FinTech firms, Challenger banks, Traditional banks, Income, Profitability, Profit.

1. Introduction:

In recent years, the financial services sector has seen an increase in the use of digital apps, speedier electronic processes, and a goal to improve client satisfaction. A slew of new payment service providers has entered the market, that provides superior user experiences and drastically alters the dynamics between established organizations (traditional financial institutions such as banks) and their customers. These newcomers are filling some of the financial institutions' traditional duties (Póta & Becsky-Nagy, 2023). Global competitiveness and digital change are driving considerable variables and complexities in the corporate scene. Competition has increased in recent years because of the increasing internationalization of markets, the rise of multinational firms, and the influence of digital networks. As a result, a company's economic performance is becoming increasingly dependent on its ability to innovate. In highly industrialized countries, innovation accounts for around half of total economic growth, making it of enormous macroeconomic importance. Innovation aptitude is no longer only a success factor; it has become a fundamental requirement for enterprises. It provides critical competitive advantages and protects against market obsolescence (Ignat, 2017). Challenger banks, which predominantly operate without physical branches and typically through mobile platforms, prioritize providing superior user experiences and competitive pricing for specialized financial services to their consumers. These innovative banks have sprouted up across Europe, with Revolut being a famous example (Marszk & Lechman, 2022).

Revolut's mission is to remove any barriers that prevent you from reaching your financial goals. They are actively developing a platform that is extremely simple to use, completely integrated, and globally accessible, to become your primary choice for financial services. They accomplish this by providing more efficient, better, and intelligent financial products continuously. Their ultimate goal is for users to be able to manage all elements of their finances, including spending, saving, investing, borrowing, and managing, with a few taps on their platform. While they have not yet reached all markets, they are motivated to do so and are dedicated to simplifying financial operations worldwide (Revolut Bank, 2023).

Revolut started as an app aimed at lowering the price of international money transfers. Storonsky, the company's founder, had considerably bigger plans from the start (Muirhead, 2023).

Revolut now provides a comprehensive range of financial services, such as payment solutions, cryptocurrency trading, savings accounts, and stock trading. They announced ambitions to expand into Brazil, India, and New Zealand in November (Muirhead, 2023).

One prominent obstacle Revolut confronts is its pursuit of a UK banking license, which has taken two years and has been subject to extensive examination. In comparison, Starling and Monzo received their licenses in just 18 months (Muirhead, 2023).

Revolut now provides a comprehensive range of financial services, such as payment solutions, cryptocurrency trading, savings accounts, and stock trading. They announced ambitions to expand into Brazil, India, and New Zealand in November. Revolut is expected to report profits in 2021, with foreign exchange operations accounting for a sizable chunk of its income. Furthermore, it is expected to have attracted roughly 20 million consumers, making it one of the largest fintech companies in the world in terms of customer base. (Muirhead, 2023).

Revolut Payments UAB was merged into Revolut Bank UAB on July 1 2022. As a result, all customers formerly linked with Revolut Payments UAB were transferred to Revolut Bank UAB and became official customers of this bank on that date (Potter., E, 2022).

The analysis of annual statement of Revolut shows that total comprehensive income, net of tax as on 31st Dec 2022 was €23,970, which is less than the comprehensive income as on 31st Dec 2021, €43254 (Revolut Bank, 2022).

It's critical to understand how Revolut Ltd. achieved rapid growth in such a short period of time by looking at things like its formation date, the foundational products it introduced, customer growth trends, the evolution of its finance statement, and an in-depth vertical and horizontal analysis of its finance statement. Knowing the consistency of income is important, which is critical for a fintech bank's long-term viability. A steady stream of money enables the bank to meet operational costs, invest in technology, and expand its offerings by attracting more customers as well as investors. It keeps track of income sources, expenses, and financial plans, allowing the organization to rectify variations from expected results. The Financial statements are useful for creditors and investors because they allow them to compare different timeframes to analyze the company's overall direction and long-term trajectory (Innovature BPO, 2023). Further, a comparative study with competitors Monzo Bank Ltd., N26, and Commerzbank (the financial statement, number of customers, and profit) will assist in analyzing the position of Revolute Bank UAB in this competitive market.

1.1. Research Objective:

- To know the products at the foundation stage, the number of customers accumulated, and funds raised that may have led to the Establishment of Revolut Bank Ltd.
- To judge the growth of the Revolut Bank UAB through its branches opened, increasing or decreasing number of customers, SWOT analysis and comparison of its growth (branches, customers and income) to its competitors in the form of challenger Banks and traditional banks.
- To identify profitability, year to year differences in the financial statement of Revolut Bank UAB since 2021 and draw a conclusion on its comparative analysis and then compare it with the comparative statement of key figures of challenger banks and traditional banks to know which bank is more profitable for investors and customers. Along with it lets Revolut Bank UAB know about its financial statement position as compared to its benchmark competitors.

- To determine different proportions in financial statements based on common size financial statements as of 30th June 2023 of Revolut Bank UAB and competitors to assist Revolut Bank UAB in deciding on any future changes in proportions, if required, based on benchmark competitors, and along with it let the Investors and customers decide the Bank for investment opportunity and take advantages of products and services based on comparison of recent financial statements.

1.2. Research Questions:

RQ1. What is the foundation of Revolut Ltd's Establishment as Revolut Bank UAB?

This question will answer Revolut Foundation in the form of initial products or products offered which started from 1st July 2015, the trend of customers from foundation to establishment and how it was able to register itself as a bank to carry out banking transactions.

RQ2. What are the different types of measures to judge the growth of Revolut Bank UAB Ltd?

The different measurements will be in the form of the following:

- 1. Different branches and Increase in the number of customers**
- 2. SWOT analysis Of Revolut Bank UAB**
- 3. Analysis of growth in customers, Income and branches as compared to Challenger banks Monzo Bank Ltd. and N26 as well as traditional bank, Commerzbank.**

A comparative study of growth in branches, customers and trends of income as compared to its competitors will not only generate an awareness of its growth as compared to its competitors, but also take steps necessary to remain ahead in competition. Further, SWOT analysis will assist in working on its weaknesses as well as threats while grasping the opportunity for the benefit of the bank and trying to keep and increase strength to escalate the longevity of the bank. On the other hand, answers of increasing branches, SWOT analysis and different comparisons with benchmarks will allow the investors and consumers to know Revolut Bank UAB in more detail, triggering them to decide on investments by Investors and take benefits of different services by customers.

RQ3. What is the final stage of analysis of comparative financial statements and Profitability Ratios ROE and ROA as of 31st December 2021, 2022 and 30th June 2023?

The Comparative analysis will be as follows:

- 1. Comparative financial statements analysis and profitability ratios of Revolut Bank UAB will be for three consecutive years.**
- 2. Comparative analysis of financial statements key figures and profitability ratios of Monzo Bank Ltd, N26 and Commerzbank and then comparison of it with Revolut Bank UAB financial statements and profitability ratios. Knowing the position of the financial**

statements of Revolut Bank UAB as compared to its competitors will help Revolut Bank UAB to know its position as well as investors to take decisions on Investment.

RQ4. What is the analysis of vertical financial statements of Revolut bank UAB as well as competitors Monzo Bank Ltd, N26 and Commerzbank as of 30th June 2023 indicates regarding the following:

- 1. The proportion of different income and expenses as compared to their Net Operating Income and does Revolut Bank UAB have adequate Income to pay operating expenses? what does the analysis with competitor states?**
- 2. Proportion of different assets and liabilities as compared to their Total Assets and to measure the adequacy of assets to ensure financial security to customers, and investors, which is further preceded by comparison of Revolut Bank UAB with its competitors.**

The analysis of the financial statements of 30th June 2023 will be able to give answers to the above questions, which will provide adequate information to investors as well as customers on whether their invested amount is safe or not. Revolut Bank UAB can make decisions to change different income and expense percentages as compared to its Net Operating Income, changes in the percentage of various assets and liabilities by considering total assets and after knowing the reasons behind increase or decrease in the cash balance, take necessary step for improvement if necessary. A comparative study of the vertical statements of competitors will let the investors, consumers and Revolut Bank UAB assess the current financial positions of all the banks and accordingly make decisions.

1.3. Value target Audience

This thesis's intended audience includes customers, investors, and Revolut Bank UAB. Knowledge of the bank's establishment, growth (customers, branches, income) and SWOT analysis can assist investors in deciding whether to invest in this bank, and consumers to use banking and other services. This may ensure safety to Investors for their investments in the form of debt, Shares bonds or other investment opportunities in the bank, along with them Revolut Bank UAB will be able to find its position as compared to its few challengers' competitors and one of the traditional banks.

The horizontal analysis of financial statements and profitability ratios of two and half years will allow the Revolut Bank UAB to know its possible changes in income, expenses, assets, liabilities and cash in the form of percentages. Evaluating the profitability ratios of this duration will assist the Investors in identifying the organization's trend of Income as compared to its equity and assets. Further, it will advise customers and investors with competitive positions allowing them to make appropriate decisions for availing services or secured investments.

Furthermore, a vertical comparison of the financial statements of Revolut Bank UAB would lead to identifying potentially harmful percentages, if any, (income and expenses, assets and liabilities, changes in cash) which may increase the chances of future losses. This will also inform investors and customers as to whether the bank is making appropriate decisions on various proportions of income and expenses, assets and liabilities, and cash balances for the survival and growth of the bank. Further, comparison with competitors will assist Revolut Bank UAB, Customers and investors in making appropriate decisions.

1.4. Scope and constraints:

The scope of this thesis is to consider competitors' data to compare and analyze the financial statements to see the position of Revolut Bank UAB in the financial market. This thesis compares the growth of Revolut Bank UAB with challenger banks Monzo Bank and N26 by taking data available from the annual reports of the respective banks. Further, the comparison is with one of the oldest traditional banks named Commerzbank, again for comparison mostly annual reports data are used as the data from annual reports are trustworthy. The banks taken into consideration for comparisons have the majority of customers and investors in Europe, the UK and the US. Therefore, these banks' valuable information is used to bring a valuable result.

The results of the comparison will be restricted to only three competitors and Revolut Bank UAB data collected. The Monzo Bank financial statements are available for the year ended February 2021 and 2022 while Revolut Bank financial statements data is available for the year ended 31st December 2021 and 2022. As a result, exact comparison is not possible between these two banks as the year ending of Monzo Bank is February. But, comparison between these two banks will at least give an overview of approximate comparison. On the other hand, the N26 data availability is only for Dec 2021 because of which a comparative financial statement analysis of this bank is not possible for the years 2021, 2022 and June 2023. While using the data of the interim year June 2023 it is assumed that the proportions of all income, expenses, assets and liabilities will be the same as the first half of the year. A comparison based on June 2023 a common-size financial statement is also impossible to calculate. The comparison of profitability ratios ROA and ROE requires either calculation as per formula or already available in the annual reports but over here only Revolut Bank UAB is providing the profitability ratios. Monzo Bank's ratios are not available in its annual report and Commerzbank's ratio on ROA is not available, therefore to have proper consistency the analysis and results of it will depend on formula-based calculated ratios, which are presented in Excel sheets of every bank.

Finally, the common size statements comparison is possible only for Commerzbank and Revolut Bank UAB as the very recent data (June 2023) of both the banks are available, which will allow

us to know the different proportions of both the banks and thereby compare to take decisions on required changes by Revolut bank UAB, if necessary, out of which Commerzbank is a traditional bank and Revolut is a challenger bank operated online.

1.5. Structure of the document

The second chapter discusses the basic concepts, already available in different kinds of literature, which provides a base for the research. This chapter starts with literature on the establishment, Growth, challenger banks, traditional banking, SWOT analysis and a brief overview of financial statements, its comparative and common size analysis as well as the components of financial statements. After providing a brief account of all foundational terminologies, further discussion is carried out on different conclusions brought by various researchers on the vital role of financial statements in making crucial decisions.

Third chapter: This chapter describes the exploratory strategy in which qualitative methodology is used to collect information on establishment, and growth in the form of number of branches and customer as well as SWOT analysis. Furthermore, quantitative methodology to collect data from external sources to know growth in Income, the position of financial statements and profitability ratios of the organizations (Revolut Bank UAB, N26, Monzo Bank and Commerzbank) in itself and comparative and common size analysis in comparison with benchmark organizations. The collection of secondary data will be analyzed to find the results in connection with research questions. The secondary sources will be based on literature on various concepts explained in chapter second

Fourth chapter: The findings of the research will be explained in the form of results by answering research questions with the help of analysis drawn in the previous chapter and then it will be interpreted and discussed to make it understandable to the target audience of the research.

Fifth chapter: Finally, this chapter will conclude the research by providing a conclusion to research answers individually for every question on the topic inside the conclusion as the synopsis. This will be further connected with Research limitations and recommendations for future research.

2. Literature review

The aim of Chapter 2 is to bring together all the background information already available through literature in the form of research articles, online newspaper articles, annual reports and other reliable sources in connection with research objectives and provide a foundation for the third chapter. The structure of this chapter is as follows:

2.1. Terminology and definitions: In this chapter, the terminologies used in this research are explained, which include establishment, challenger bank/ fintech Bank, traditional banking, financial statements analysis, components of financial statements, comparative financial statements, common-size financial statements and SWOT analysis.

2.2 Theoretical background: A brief explanation of works of literature on financial statements importance are explained and the cases on SWOT analysis of competitors are presented in brief to serve as a base for the SWOT analysis of Revolut bank UAB.

2.1. Terminology and definitions:

2.1.1. Establishment:

An establishment is a single location committed to a single core activity, whereas a corporation is a company or group of companies involved in financial activities across multiple industries. An organization may use a single or many Employer Identification Numbers (EINs) to submit reports (Sadeghi et al., 2016).

Furthermore, many laws involve fixed costs rather than merely variable (per-unit) charges, and larger enterprises can spread fixed costs across a larger output volume. As a result, if rules are implemented uniformly across all organizations within a particular sector, we can expect that expenses, regardless of firm size, will be higher for smaller firms than for larger ones (Chambers et al., 2022). Small businesses dominate the American economy as far as total numbers of establishments and employees are concerned. According to the US Census Bureau's "Statistics of US Firms" (SUSB), a small business is defined as one with less than 500 employees by the Small Business Administration (SBA), and this definition accounts for 99.7% of US firms and 47.5% of US employment. In terms of innovation, small businesses frequently surpass their larger competitors. Small businesses are an important instrument for economic mobility, especially for low-income families with limited access to credit. Regulations may limit the economic opportunities accessible to low-income households to the point that they hurt small businesses or create entry obstacles. To address these concerns, Congress put small business relief provisions into the regulatory process. For example, the Regulatory Flexibility Act of 1980 and the Small Business Regulatory Enforcement Fairness Act of 1996 (Chambers et al., 2022).

Contemporary internationalization research increasingly emphasizes that the diversity of enterprises might contribute to conflicting findings about the mode of entry. This decision applies to when and under what conditions a company decides to expand into a foreign country, either by establishing a new operation from scratch or by acquiring a company (Boellis et al., 2016). Multiunit organizations, rather than operating as a group of distinct businesses, work as a coherent unit (Sadeghi et al., 2016). Because of this cohesiveness, larger multiunit organizations may make more centralized decisions when it comes to measures such as managing recruitment, closing a plant or store, or cutting their personnel during economic downturns (Sadeghi et al., 2016). Businesses make these decisions based on the financial sustainability of certain locations, the breadth of products or services offered, and the possible long-term benefits to the business as a whole (Sadeghi et al., 2016). It is illegal under European Union (EU) law to place limits on a member nation's freedom of establishment when it operates on the territory of another member state. This restriction also applies to nationals of any EU member state establishing agencies, branches, or subsidiaries on the territory of another

member state. The interpretation of this topic is principally determined by the European Court of Justice (ECJ), which serves as the highest legal authority on establishment freedom. Fair and healthy competition principles, as well as guaranteeing equitable access for all firms, are inextricably tied to freedom of establishment. As a result, any restrictions on the freedom of individuals or firms from one EU member state to establish themselves in another member state's territory are illegal. This prohibition also includes any restrictions on persons or firms from any EU member state establishing agencies, branches, or subsidiaries on the territory of another member state. The interpretation of these issues by the ECJ is critical because it is the basic legal framework governing the freedom of company establishment within the EU (Tushevskva, 2015).

2.1.2. Incorporation:

Company formation is a more involved process. It entails the formation of a separate legal organization, often known as a corporation, with its own distinct identity independent from its owners. This distinct legal position enables the corporation to own assets, enter into contractual agreements, and file legal actions in its name (EAdvisors, 2023).

The process of forming a company often includes submitting articles of incorporation to the appropriate governmental authority, whether at the state or federal level. Typically, these articles of incorporation include information on the corporation's name, purpose, organizational structure, and governance. It also entails the appointment of a board of directors and the distribution of stock to the company's owners, known as shareholders (EAdvisors, 2023).

2.1.3. Registration:

The formal procedure of enrolling your firm with the relevant regulatory authorities is known as company registration. This usually requires filling out a registration form and paying a fee. The fundamental goal of company registration is to provide your firm with legal status, allowing you to open a bank account, acquire financing, and enter into contractual agreements (EAdvisors, 2023).

Business registration is typically a simple process that may be completed online or with the assistance of a business registration professional. In most cases, you'll be asked to provide basic information about your firm, such as its name, location, and business structure (sole proprietorship, partnership, or limited liability corporation). After the registration is completed, you will be issued a certificate of registration, proving that your company is lawfully registered and authorized to operate (EAdvisors, 2023).

2.1.4. Challenger banks or fintech banks:

Through digital innovations, the financial sector has undergone a substantial transition, resulting in the reinvention of business models and retail services. Challenger banks, which represent a type of

financial innovation, have emerged as a notable example of this transition. These banks and FinTech firms operate in the digital arena, disrupting the traditional, huge, and established banking institutions. They pioneer a new approach to financial services delivery, emphasizing the importance of agility in their organizational structure and exploiting cutting-edge technologies as fundamental drivers of their success (Marszk & Lechman, 2022).

2.1.5. Traditional banking:

Traditional banking is a well-established paradigm with a long history that includes the provision of banking services through physical bank branches. This long-lasting system has grown over time and now includes functions like accepting deposits, making loans, issuing credit cards, and facilitating transactions. Banks provide a wide range of financial services, such as checking and savings accounts, mortgages and commercial loans. Traditional banking has aided economic progress by providing individuals and businesses with loans and financial assistance. However, it has recently faced significant challenges as a result of the rise of digital banking and fintech businesses (Devendra et al., 2022)

2.1.6. Growth:

According to the financial dictionary, in the world of finance, the phrase "growth" can refer to a variety of things, such as business development, increased investment, or a country's general economic advancement. Growth, regardless of the context, often denotes a positive development with considerable benefits for businesses, investors, and the greater economy. In contrast, "negative growth" is frequently associated with economic downturns such as depressions and recessions, during which the economy contracts and decreases.

Successful companies thrive while unsuccessful ones decline. Competent managers understand that achieving growth is dependent on customer-centric approaches. This includes not only recruiting new consumers, but also maintaining existing ones, inspiring more spending from them, and persuading them to advocate for your goods among their networks. Recognizing that consumers are the key driver of profitable growth is a fundamental principle (Keiningham et al., 2008).

Businesses enter overseas markets for a variety of reasons, with one of the most common being the pursuit of corporate growth and expansion. Economic globalization is the process through which businesses rapidly expand their market reach to include a global client base. This level of development has been made possible, in large part, by technological advances that arose during the twentieth century, making international connections and interactions more accessible. According to All Business expert William Edwards, becoming global can minimize an organization's dependency on local and national markets. In other words, a fall in domestic consumer demand can be compensated by an increase in demand from overseas customers (Twarowska & Curie-Sk, n.d.).

2.1.7. Financial Statements analysis:

Financial statements analysis is a systematic and logical technique for displaying a company's overall financial performance to assist in financial decision-making for business operations. It is the basic and logical framework that stakeholders use to evaluate a company. This study entails closely evaluating financial statements to acquire a thorough grasp of the firm's status and performance (Murthy, BS et al., 2018). The word "financial analysis" refers to both "analysis" and "interpretation." Analysis is the methodical organizing and simplification of financial data as reported in financial statements, whereas interpretation is the elucidation of the resulting data's purpose and significance (National Council of Education Research and Training, 2023)

Financial information is critical in the business world because it allows users to predict the quantity, timing, and predictability of cash flows, which in turn guides their decision-making. Financial statements, like any language, are primarily used for communication. When working with financial data, it is critical to utilize the proper, exact, and correct language (Barry & Jamie, 2011).

Financial statements are a source of data and facts about the success of banks in developing countries such as the United States of America (USA). As a result, the goal of financial analysis is to give evidence of a bank's financial status, achievement of planned objectives, and capacity to effectively solve economic difficulties, particularly in servicing the demands of customers (Barry & Jamie, 2011).

Financial statements are used in European commercial banks to publicly portray the bank's actions, providing real proof and insights into the bank's achievements, important issues, and methods used to overcome these challenges. As a result, financial analysis knowledge and expertise are essential for a variety of persons, including investors, creditors, and regulatory bodies (Berthilde & Rusibana, 2020).

In Africa, the major goal of financial statements is to offer financial information to stakeholders. In this regard, the Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB) is in charge of developing worldwide accounting standards (David, 2006).

Just as baseball players who can't keep score are at a disadvantage, operational managers who don't understand accounting and financial principles are at a disadvantage when it comes to negotiating the working conditions in these domains (Berthilde & Rusibana, 2020).

2.1.8. Components of financial Statements

A bank's annual report must evaluate its progress in reaching its objectives by delivering major financial statements. The balance sheet, profit and loss statements, statements representing changes in stakeholder equity, and cash flow statements are all examples of these statements (Solberg & Durrieu, 2006).

Income Statement: In income statement analysis, the profit and loss account shows a summary of a company's financial activities over a given period, outlining revenues collected and providing a brief picture of the company's financial status and operational performance (Murthy et al., 2018).

Balance Sheet: The balance sheet is frequently compared to a snapshot since it provides a detailed view of a company's financial status at a certain point in time. It depicts both the current and historical situation of the company, allowing readers of financial statements to see any positive changes that may have happened (Ojo, 2012). In the case of balance sheet analysis, financial statements provide useful information to stakeholders by reflecting the financial position at a given point in time, including the structure of assets, liabilities, and owners' equity (Murthy. BS et al., 2018).

Statement of Changes in Equity: Changes in shareholder equity are caused by changes in the equity part of the balance sheet over time. These changes are often caused by gains or losses, dividend distributions, and stock issuance (Ebimobowei, 2012).

The cash flow statement tracks the changes in cash as a result of a company's business operations. As an outcome, cash flow analysis is critical in making informed investment decisions and guaranteeing the smooth operation of a corporation (Berthilde & Rusibana, 2020)

2.1.9. Comparative financial Statements analysis:

Individuals evaluate consecutive balance sheets, income statements, or statements of cash flows over various periods in comparative financial statements analysis. This often requires a detailed review of changes in specific account balances over a year or multiple years. The major insight acquired through comparative financial statements analysis is the identification of trends across time. This study assists individuals in understanding how a company's financial performance and position have changed over time, and it gives useful insights for decision-making and strategic planning. When evaluating comparative financial statements, we examine account balances from left to right or right to left, which is known as horizontal analysis. This type of analysis focuses on how financial data changes over time, emphasizing horizontal mobility in the statements. Two extensively utilized methodologies in comparative financial statements analysis are year-to-year change analysis and index-number trend analysis (Haider, 2020).

When comparing financial accounts over relatively short periods, usually two to three years, year-to-year change analysis is used. The year-to-year fluctuations in individual accounts are examined using this method. For short periods, year-to-year change analysis is preferable since it is more manageable and easier to comprehend. This method has the advantage of providing insights into changes in both absolute dollar amounts and percentages, making it a versatile tool for financial analysis (Haider, 2020).

Index-number trend analysis, like calculating year-to-year percentage changes, may not effectively portray certain changes, notably those involving transitions from negative to positive amounts. Index statistics may not accurately convey the amount of the shift in such circumstances (Haider, 2020).

2.1.10. Profitability ratios:

Bank managers and system analysts frequently evaluate a bank's profitability using indicators such as return on equity (ROE) and return on assets (ROA). A bank is considered high-performing when its indicators regularly outperform the banking system's average over an extended period. ROE measures the return on investment made by shareholders, with higher levels indicating the possibility of larger dividends from management. Furthermore, rising ROE lays the groundwork for rising future returns (Munteanu et al., 2021)

Return on Assets (ROA) is computed by dividing net income by total assets, which is frequently done using average values. The percentage return on each monetary unit of asset is calculated using this metric. It is vital to highlight in the arena of analysis that a greater ROA indicates improved profitability for a bank. The ROA measure values differ between banks, owing to differences in commission levels (Manimekalai and Gauri, 2022).

2.1.11. Common-size financial statements:

Understanding the proportion of a given account within a group or subgroup can help with financial statements analysis. When reviewing a balance sheet, the total assets (or total liabilities plus equity) are typically written as 100%, and individual accounts within these categories are expressed as a percentage of the totals. When reviewing an income statements, sales are frequently set to 100%, with the remaining income statements accounts expressed as a percentage of sales. This method assures that the total of individual accounts within groups always equals 100%, resulting in what are known as common-size financial statements. This method is also known as vertical analysis because it involves the up-down or down-up examination of accounts in common-size statements. Common-size financial statements analysis is useful for learning about the internal structure of financial statements. For example, when employing common-size analysis to examine a balance sheet, it emphasizes two crucial factors:

- Financing sources include the allocation of funds among current liabilities, noncurrent liabilities, and equity.
- Asset composition entails breaking down individual current and noncurrent assets to better understand their relative importance within the financial framework (Haider, 2020).
- In order to allow for comparability between companies, common statements are particularly valuable because they standardize the financial statements from each company into a common size format. It is easier to distinguish between variations in the composition and distribution of accounts when a company's common size statements are used against those of its competitors or industry average (Haider, 2020).

2.1.12. SWOT Analysis:

A SWOT analysis is a useful technique for identifying important strengths and opportunities (Keshta et al., 2022). SWOT analysis, which stands for Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats, is a popular tool for systematically examining both internal and external situations, providing an organized approach to decision-making. It entails assessing strategic elements, which include both internal and external features critical to an organization's future performance and are defined in the SWOT analysis. The ultimate goal of the strategic planning process, of which SWOT analysis is a component, is to develop and implement a strategy that effectively aligns with the interplay of internal and external factors. SWOT analysis is especially useful when a strategy alternative emerges unexpectedly, prompting a study of the decision context surrounding it (Kurttila et al., 2000). External influences can be classified as "opportunities" based on their attraction and chance of success. Furthermore, they can be classed as "threats" based on their severity and likelihood of occurrence. Internal factors can be ranked depending on their performance and relevance, with "strengths" and "weaknesses" distinguished. SWOT analysis can be done at the level of certain organizational units, allowing for a more in-depth assessment of internal and external issues inside various parts of the organization (Kurttila et al., 2000). Internal aspects, which include assets and expertise, are classified as strengths (S) or weaknesses (W) in a SWOT analysis. Here are a few instances of typical internal factors:

Financing, income streams, and investment prospects, as well as physical assets such as location, services, and technology, are all necessary resources (Kurttila et al., 2000).

Workforce, contributions and the intended audience are all examples of human resources (Kurttila et al., 2000).

Access to natural resources, intellectual property rights such as trademarks, patents, and copyrights, as well as employee initiatives, departmental structures, and software systems, are examples of existing processes (Kurttila et al., 2000).

External forces have an impact on every business, organization, and individual. It is critical to identify and document each of these characteristics, whether they are directly or indirectly related to opportunities (O) or dangers (T) (Kurttila et al., 2000).

External factors frequently include aspects beyond your or your organization's control, such as Market trends (product developments, technology advances, and adjustments in client needs) Economic trends (local, national, and global financial trends) Donations, legislation, and other financial resources are examples of funding sources. Demographic shifts Relationships with suppliers and partners At various levels of government, there are political, environmental, and economic rules (Kurttila et al., 2000).

Combining SWOT-TOWS analysis with many other analytical methodologies helps quick and easy decision-making when selecting the most advantageous strategy for executing expansion. However,

it is still necessary to apply it in conjunction with other analytical tools (Brycht & Ulewicz, 2023). Following the creation of the SWOT framework and completion of the SWOT analysis, it is critical to put recommendations and strategies based on the results into action (Skye Schooley, 2023).

2.2. Theoretical background

2.2.1. Literatures on Importance of analyzing financial Statements:

M. Berthilde and C. Rusibana's 2020 financial statements study focused on the Bank of Kigali and its implications for investment decisions. Their findings highlight the significance of financial statement analysis for both individuals and enterprises, particularly in avoiding the significant risks associated with beginning and growing a firm. The researchers used horizontal analysis as a crucial tool to examine the Bank of Kigali's financial records from 2014 to 2018. This strategy enabled the bank to compare its business performance across that period, providing useful information for decision-making. Furthermore, the study found that ratio analysis is widely used at the Bank of Kigali and is an important part of their financial analysis process. Furthermore, common size analysis is commonly used, with 55% of respondents reporting that it is used extensively within the bank.

In conclusion, the financial statement analysis performed for the Bank of Kigali was critical in improving the bank's investment decision-making. It offered information about the bank's financial performance and aided in determining the bank's viability for various investment opportunities (Berthilde & Rusibana, 2020)

Dalnial et al.'s 2014 study sought to evaluate the association between financial statements analysis and fraudulent financial reporting. The study's findings found that certain financial ratios, particularly the total debt to total asset ratio and the receivables to revenue ratio, were identified as strong indicators of fraudulent financial reporting. This implies that financial ratios can be useful instruments for detecting instances of fake financial reporting. These findings add to the body of evidence supporting the effectiveness of financial ratios in fraud detection.

Dr. S. Poongavanam emphasizes the significance of financial accounts through comparative analysis. This entails looking at trends in the same financial items and computed figures across various financial statements from the same organization on different dates. Efficient financial management is important to the success of any business.

The concept of financial performance is dynamic and ever-changing. In today's business world, there is an increasing emphasis on measuring and improving financial performance. Dr. S. Poongavanam's research focuses on the financial performance of one company in particular, Mahindra Finance Ltd (Punjabi, 2019)

Manimekalai and Gauri undertook a comparative examination of the financial performance of India's two main sectors, namely private and public sector banks. The researchers evaluated the banks using a variety of financial criteria, including net profit, assets, liabilities, income, expenses, margin

ratios, and return on equity ratios. The data for the study ranged from 2017 to 2021 (Manimekalai and Gauri, 2022).

According to the research findings, private-sector banks outperformed their public-sector rivals throughout this period. This means that private banks' financial performance was typically stronger, as evidenced by the specified financial criteria.

2.2.2. Case studies of Benchmarks SWOT, forming base for SWOT analysis of Revolut Bank UAB

SWOT analysis of N26 Bank:

N26 was formed in 2013 in Berlin by Valentin Stalf and Maximilian Tayenthal with the purpose of pioneering modern, 100% digital banking. In 2015, they made a critical milestone by establishing Europe's first mobile bank accounts, demonstrating that handling money on the go can be straightforward, easy, and transparent. N26 got a full banking license in 2016, allowing it to spread its services to 17 other countries. N26 also guaranteed that their customers' funds were legally protected, with each customer's deposits being protected up to €100,000 by the German Deposit Protection Scheme. N26 had attained a spectacular milestone of 2 million customers in 24 countries by 2018. LinkedIn acknowledged their accomplishments by naming them as the best startup to work for in Germany. In 2021, Forbes named N26 the Best Bank in the World, a notable honor in the financial business. This year, N26 also became Germany's highest-valued fintech business after a \$900+ million Series E fundraising round, culminating in a valuation of more than \$9 billion. N26 reached a new milestone in 2022 when they reached their 8 millionth customer. They also went beyond regular banking by developing N26 Crypto, a foray into the realm of investments and cryptocurrency. This step highlighted their commitment to changing the financial landscape and offering a broader choice of financial services to their consumers (About N26 | the First Bank You'll Love, n.d.).

Strengths:

- **Rapid Expansion of Customer Base:** The company's customer base has grown rapidly and significantly.
- **Key Partnerships with Prominent Industries:** The company has effectively formed collaborations with top organizations in a variety of industries.
- **Enhanced Flexibility and Agility in contrast to Traditional Banks:** The organization is more adaptable and agile in contrast to traditional financial institutions.
- **Customer Experience is prioritized in its business model:** The company's business model prioritizes providing an amazing client experience.

- Consistent funding rounds resulted in the highest valuation in Europe: The company has continuously received substantial capital in subsequent rounds, propelling it to become Europe's most valuable brand (SWOT & PESTLE, 2023).

Weaknesses:

- Lack of Integration of Traditional Banking Fundamental Features: The organization has struggled to incorporate key features of traditional banking services into its products.
- Concerns and Criticisms About Identity Verification Procedures: The organization has received critical feedback and scrutiny about its techniques for identifying and validating clients.
- Fraudulent Transactions that resulted in Regulatory Sanctions: The occurrence of fraudulent transactions resulted in regulatory authorities issuing orders and penalties on the company.
- Sustainability is being called into question, as profit is not a primary metric: The company's reliance on indicators other than profitability may call into question the company's long-term viability (SWOT & PESTLE, 2023).

Opportunities:

- Diversification into Online Trading and Other Financial Services: Neobanks like as N26 have the ability to expand their portfolio of banking services and provide clients greater options and convenience.
- Market Expansion to Increase Customer Base and Market Share: N26 has the opportunity to enter new markets, which could result in an enlarged customer base and a greater market share. This expansion will help the company's growth and reach (SWOT & PESTLE, 2023).

Threats:

- Strong competition in a crowded market due to the emergence of numerous Neo banks offering diverse products: The extremely competitive climate is exacerbated by the ongoing entry of new Neo banks offering a diverse range of financial products (SWOT & PESTLE, 2023).

SWOT analysis of Monzo Bank:

Monzo Bank Ltd is a UK-based online bank and one of the country's first new-app-based challenger banks (Kobie, 2019). The bank primarily works through digital methods, including a mobile app and the provision of a prepaid debit card to users. Monzo expanded its services in April 2017, following the relaxation of UK banking licensing limitations (Monzo, 2017).

Monzo Bank had a customer base of over 4 million members as of March 2020. However, the bank reported a huge net loss of £113.8 million over that period, a significant rise from the previous year's net loss of £47.1 million (O'Hear, 2015).

Strengths:

- Intuitive Mobile App: Monzo Bank provides a user-friendly mobile app that improves the customer experience.
- High Level of Transparency: The bank is dedicated to transparency in its operations and services.
- Monzo Bank provides sympathetic and customer-centric services, addressing the wants and concerns of its customers.
- Community Engagement for Growth and Development: The bank actively engages its community in influencing its growth and development, encouraging participation and collaboration.
- Fee-Free overseas Transactions: Monzo Bank offers fee-free overseas transactions, making international financial operations more affordable.
- Strong Brand Reputation: The bank has established a strong and well-known brand in the business and among its clients (Issuu., 2021).

Weaknesses:

- Monzo Bank's marketing and promotional efforts are somewhat limited, which may hinder its visibility and customer acquisition.
- Exclusive Mobile Access: Because the bank primarily provides services through a mobile platform, consumers who prefer other channels may be limited in their access.
- Monzo may experience difficulty in attaining profitability or financial returns, which could influence its long-term survival.
- High customer support charges may put a burden on the bank's financial resources and operational effectiveness (Issuu, 2021).

Opportunities:

- Substantial Growth Possibility: Monzo Bank offers plenty of space for market expansion and growth.
- Branding and Promoting: The bank has the potential to spend in advertising and marketing initiatives to increase brand visibility and attract new clients.
- Add-On Elements: The bank can supplement its present offers with new features and services, expanding its product line.
- Strategic Planning Partnerships: Forming alliances with other enterprises and organizations can provide new opportunities for growth and collaboration.
- Overseas Expansion: Increasing its consumer base and global presence by expanding into international markets (Issuu., 2021).

Threats:

- High Customer assistance Costs: The high costs of customer assistance can put a burden on the bank's financial resources and operational effectiveness.
- Challenges in reaching Financial Returns: The bank may experience challenges in generating profits or reaching the desired financial returns, which could jeopardize its long-term existence.
- Competitive Environment: The presence of significant competitors in the market threatens Monzo Bank's market share and growth possibilities (Issuu., 2021).

SWOT Analysis of Commerzbank:

Commerzbank is one of Germany's largest banks, having a long history extending back to its founding in Hamburg in 1870. It evolved and expanded its operations over time, with a special concentration on Berlin around 1900. By 1940, the bank was formally known as "Commerzbank Aktiengesellschaft." (Krause, 2022).

Commerzbank has long been a fixture in the German banking and financial landscape. Individuals, businesses, and institutions have all benefited from the bank's services. Its enormous branch network and services have propelled it to the top of the country's big banks (Felsing, 2023).

Commerzbank highlights its dedication to providing its customers with protection and support, particularly during difficult times, while also assisting them in seizing new chances and prospects. The bank has positioned itself as "the bank for Germany," emphasizing its role in collaboratively shaping the future with consumers (Felsing, 2023).

Commerzbank has a long history of involvement in banking and financial services, including retail banking, corporate banking, investment banking, and asset management. Its history and reputation have elevated it to a key position in Germany's financial sector (Felsing, 2023).

Commerzbank, located in Frankfurt/Main, is Germany's second-largest bank, providing a diverse variety of global banking services. The bank employs about 52,000 people (Aier et al., 2015)

Strengths:

- Commerzbank is Germany's second-largest bank, reflecting its substantial presence and influence in the financial system (Team, 2020).
- The bank has a dense and extended branch network, allowing it to serve a diverse spectrum of clients across the country (Team, 2020).
- Commerzbank is often recognized as the best bank for small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) in Germany, owing to its personalized services and support for this key sector of the economy (Team, 2020).
- The bank serves over 15 million private consumers and 1 million business and corporate clients worldwide, demonstrating its capacity to meet the needs of a wide range of customers (Team, 2020).

- Commerzbank is a market leader in the online banking sector, providing consumers with a convenient and robust digital banking experience (Team, 2020).
- Within the German financial scene, the bank has created a strong and recognised brand position, instilling trust and confidence in its clients (Team, 2020).

Weaknesses:

- Retail Banking Dominance: Commerzbank's retail banking operations produce a sizable amount of its revenue. This demonstrates that the bank succeeds in serving individual and small business clients by providing a diverse variety of retail banking services (Team, 2020).
- Limited Investment Banking Revenue: While Commerzbank has a presence in investment banking, this activity accounts for a significantly lesser portion of its revenue. This implies that it is primarily concerned with ordinary banking services rather than investment banking (Team, 2020).
- Limited Asian and American Presence: Commerzbank has a comparatively poor presence in Asian and American countries. This means that its global reach and revenue are predominantly centered in European markets, particularly Germany (Team, 2020).

Opportunities:

- Collaborating with other banks can help Commerzbank expand its service offerings and client base. The bank can better satisfy the changing demands of its clients and even reach new customer segments by merging resources and expertise (Team, 2020).
- As a strategic approach, Commerzbank can use partnerships and acquisitions to enter the lucrative Asian and American markets. Partnerships or acquisitions can help the bank establish a more significant presence and a stronger foothold in these regions, which offer tremendous growth prospects (Team, 2020).

Threats:

- Any regulatory changes in the Eurozone will have an impact on Commerzbank. These modifications may have an impact on the bank's operations, capital requirements, and regulatory duties. The bank's stability and competitiveness must keep up with and react to changing rules (Team, 2020).
- A slowdown in the Eurozone's economic growth and investment can have a significant influence on Commerzbank's performance. It could result in lower demand for financial services and credit, affecting the bank's income and profitability. The bank's prosperity is inextricably linked to the economic health of the region in which it operates (Team, 2020).

2.2.3. Establishment as Revolut bank UAB

Revolut Ltd, a London-based firm founded in 2015, specializes in online money transfers, currency conversion, card payments, and global cash withdrawals (Appendix 1. B).

They raised \$15 million in Series A funding in 2016 and achieved 100,000 individual clients (About Us | Revolut, n.d.).

The next year, in 2017, they raised \$66 million in a Series B investment round. In addition, It launched new services in the European Economic Area (EEA), including Revolut Business, Revolut Premium, and Crypto Trading (About Us | Revolut, n.d.).

In 2018, Revolut reached a crucial milestone when the Bank of Lithuania gave them a banking license. During the same year, they also introduced Revolut Metal and raised an amazing \$250 million in a Series C investment round (About Us | Revolut, n.d.). By the end of 2018, the company reached three million customers (Grut, 2019).

Revolut got incorporated as REVOLUT LTD on 6th December 2013 with company No. 8804411 and proposed registered office 60 Arnhem Wharf, Arnhem Place, London, Great Britain, E143RU (REVOLUT LTD Filing History - Find and Update Company Information - GOV.UK, n.d.)

Nikolay Storonsky and Vlad Yatsenko founded the finance business Revolut in July 2015 at the Level39 tech accelerator in Canary Wharf (Russon, 2019). Revolut, which debuted in the United Kingdom in 2015, provides money transfer and exchange services. (Revolut, 2023).

28 Aug 2014 Registered office address changed from 60 Arnhem Wharf Arnhem Place London E14 3RU Great Britain to 1 Canada Square Level 39, 1 Canada Square London E14 5AB on 28 August 2014 (Appendix 1. A).

On 13 December 2018, the European Central Bank granted Revolut Technologies UAB a specialized banking license based on the evaluation and recommendation of Lithuania's financial regulatory authorities. Concurrently, the Board of the Bank of Lithuania granted Revolut Payments UAB an electronic money institution license. Both of these companies are related to Revolut Ltd (Appendix 1B)

Revolut Technologies UAB is planning to take deposits and issue consumer loans after obtaining a specialized bank license. A fundamental distinction between a specialized bank and a full-service bank is that the former is not permitted to provide investment services (Appendix 1. B).

Meanwhile, Revolut Payments UAB intends to issue electronic money and provide a broad range of payment services, including card payments, direct debits, credit transfers, cash withdrawals, money transmissions, payment initiation, and account information services (Appendix 1. B).

The Revolut Bank UAB was registered on 13th December 2021(Appendix 1. A). Revolut Bank UAB is a Lithuanian bank with the registration number 304580906 and the authorization code LB002119,

and its official location is Konstitucijos Ave. 21B, 08130 Vilnius, Lithuania. It is governed and regulated by the Bank of Lithuania and the European Central Bank, both of which have licensed it as a credit institution. Its license may be verified on the Bank of Lithuania's website, and its incorporation and business records can be accessed on the Lithuanian Register of Legal Entities' website. The Bank of Lithuania, with the registry number 188607684, operates as both the central bank and the financial regulatory authority of Lithuania. It is located at Gedimino Ave. 6, 01103 Vilnius, Lithuania (Personal Terms | Revolut DE, n.d.).

Revolut Payments UAB was merged into Revolut Bank UAB on July 1, 2022. As a result, all customers formerly linked with Revolut Payments UAB were transferred to Revolut Bank UAB and became official customers of this bank on that date (Potter., E, 2022).

Revolut previously operated in Ireland under an e-money license. Before Brexit, it used an e-money license that it had transferred from its UK operations to Ireland. Following Brexit, it did the same with a license transferred from its Lithuanian operations (Cassidy, 2022)

The EU passporting regulations allowed financial institutions and banks licensed in one EU country to transfer that license to another, allowing them to operate there without requiring full regulatory permission again (Cassidy, 2022).

However, as an e-money institution rather than a bank, Revolut was not covered by the Deposit Guarantee Scheme or the 'bank guarantee.' It was also unable to make loans (Cassidy, 2022).

Revolut has been operating in Ireland under its Lithuanian banking license since March 2022. Despite obtaining a Lithuanian banking license in 2018, it continued to operate for several years in Ireland and other countries under an e-money license. This layout has now been altered (Cassidy, 2022).

Toward the end of the previous year 2021, the specialized EU banking license was upgraded to include a full banking license. As a result, Revolut Bank UAB is now authorized to provide payment services in addition to deposit-taking and loan-granting services. This expansion opened the path for the merger and assures that Revolut Bank UAB can continue to provide creative new products and services to all of its clients (Potter, 2023) (Appendix 1. C).

The global FinTech industry has taken notice of its message, as the Bank of Lithuania serves as a welcoming regulatory authority that encourages innovation and provides one of the shortest licensing processes in the European Union. According to Marius Jurgilas, a Board Member of the Bank of Lithuania, as a result, there has been a considerable surge in the excitement of both local and foreign firms to launch and extend their worldwide FinTech projects in Lithuania. (Lietuvos Bankas, 2017) & (Appendix 1.D).

The above literature review will provide answer to RQ. 1

2.2.4. Growth of Revolut Bank UAB

Different branches and Increase in the number of customers

➤ Branches

Revolut Bank UAB registered Branches in the EU are as follows:

- Revolut Bank UAB (Belgian Branch), which was incorporated on 19th April 2021, registered address: Louise Centre, Stephanie Square Centre, Avenue Louise 65, 1050 Brussels, Belgium.
- Revolut Bank UAB (Netherlands Branch), which was incorporated on 9th August 2022, registered address: Avenue Barbara Strozzi 201, 1083HN Amsterdam, Netherlands
- Revolut Bank UAB (Sp z o.o.) Oddział w Polsce (Polish Branch), which was incorporated on 26th January 2021, registered address: Podium Park, al. Jana Pawła II, 43a, 31-864 Kraków, Polska
- Revolut Bank UAB - Sucursal em Portugal (Portugal Branch), which was incorporated on 18th May 2022, registered address: Sitio, Rua do Campo Alegre, 774 Distrito: Porto Concelho: Porto Freguesia: Lordelo do Ouro e Massarelos 4150 171 Porto, Portugal.
- Revolut Bank UAB Magyarországi Fióktelepe (Hungarian Branch), which was incorporated on 14th January 2021, registered address: Radnóti Miklós utca 2, 1137 Budapest, Hungary
- Revolut France succursale de Revolut Bank UAB (French Branch), which was incorporated on 12th July 2022, registered address: 3 Rue de Stockholm (Patchwork) Saint Lazare, 75008 Paris, France
- Revolut Bank UAB (Irish Branch), which was incorporated on 4th May 2022, registered address: 2 Dublin Landings, North Dock, Dublin 1, Ireland
- Revolut Italia, Branch di Revolut Bank UAB (Italian Branch), which was incorporated on 19th April 2022, registered address: Via Archievescovo, Calabiana, 6, 20139 Milano, Italy
- Revolut Bank UAB, Zweigniederlassung Deutschland, Germany, which was incorporated on 17th January 2023, registered address: Gontardstraße 11, 10178 Berlin, Germany
- Revolut Bank UAB Sucursal En España, which was incorporated on 7th March 2023, registered address: C/ Serrano 20 - Cloudworks Madrid, 28001 Madrid, Spain. NIF code W0250845E.

Revolut Group aspires to provide a global financial super application that provides retail and business clients with access to a growing range of financial services. These services are intended to exceed traditional banks in terms of speed and quality, while also giving consumers more control over their financial affairs (Revolut, 2022).

There are no physical branches and all customer support is provided via mobile app/web-app chat (Revolut, 2022).

➤ **Customers:**

In 2016 the total number of customers was 100000, but in the year 2019, it reached 10 million customers and then escalated to 14.5 million in the year 2020 (About Us | Revolut, n.d.), which further grew to 25 million in the year 2022 and up till June 2023 it grew by 5 million and reached to 30 million customers (Revolut, 2023).

➤ **SWOT analysis Of Revolut Bank UAB**

Strengths: Increase in number of customers from 100000 in the year 2016 to 25 million in the year 2022 and then Revolut has 30 million retail customers worldwide, with a further five million joining since November 2022. (About Us | Revolut, n.d.) and (Revolut, 2023).

The number of monthly transactions made by Revolut's customer base has surpassed 400 million, up from 350 million in November 2022 (Revolut, 2023).

Revolut offers money transfer and currency conversion services. Currently, the organization welcomes roughly one million new consumers each month. More than 30 million retail consumers worldwide have access to a variety of innovative Revolut products, including peer-to-peer payments, Saving Vaults, 18 accounts, and stays for holiday reservations. Please keep in mind that terms and limitations apply (Revolut, 2023).

Revolut uses technology to address the issues traditionally associated with banking, providing a diverse range of services geared to modern financial needs (Ferreira, 2023)

Increasing series of funding: 2018: Series C fundraising raises \$250m, 2020 Series D fundraising raises \$580m, 2021-Raised Series E funding of \$800m, to continue to build the first global financial super app

Storonsky's comments align with a trend in European fintech companies shifting their efforts toward profitability rather than expansion as new investment becomes more difficult to come by. However, he fiercely denied rumors that Revolut had enough funding to last only two years, claiming that the fintech startup does not have a pressing need to raise further capital. (O'Brien, 2023).

Weaknesses: There are no physical facilities, and all customer service is provided through chat features on mobile and web applications (Revolut, 2022).

According to reports, thieves exploited a flaw in Revolut's payment system in the United States, stealing more than \$20 million. According to sources familiar with the situation, as described by the Financial Times, this money was stolen over months due to differences in Revolut's payment systems between the United States and Europe (Isaacs, 2023).

The problem came from the fact that certain transactions that were initially denied were later incorrectly paid using Revolut's funds. Importantly, the stolen monies came from the fintech company itself, not from customer deposits. Despite retrieving around \$23 million, Revolut nonetheless suffered a net loss of approximately \$20 million (Isaacs, 2023).

Following its discovery toward the end of 2021, criminal organizations allegedly began abusing this payment bug in early 2022. Individuals were allegedly urged to make high-value transactions that were denied, and then cash out the money at ATMs (Isaacs, 2023).

Opportunities:

The bank is focused on implementing its strategy, which includes offering a variety of consumer finance choices in all European Union markets, with a particular emphasis on adapting services to local needs (Revolut, 2022).

Furthermore, Revolut Bank UAB is in the process of getting a Swiss Representative Office license from FINMA, Switzerland's regulatory office, to provide banking services to Swiss consumers. Once FINMA grants this license, Revolut Ltd's current client base in Switzerland will be transferred to the bank. The Representative Office will primarily promote the bank's services in Switzerland, and new Swiss customers will be registered directly with the bank (Revolut, 2022).

Threats:

The Revolut event emphasizes the opportunistic nature of cyberattacks, emphasizing attackers' willingness to exploit any weakness for data and financial loss. If there is a weakness, it becomes a target (Selina Coen, 2023).

These attacks frequently begin at the human-computer interaction. In the case of Revolut, the breach was caused by the financial gain from the manipulation of a process defect. Attacks on banks and other financial institutions, on the other hand, usually involve the use of human activities, operational processes, and computer systems. According to Statistica statistics, financial institutions (FIs) are especially vulnerable to phishing attempts, which is consistent with the findings of the DBIR study,

which demonstrates a significant link between stolen credentials and data breaches (Selina Coen, 2023).

2.2.5. Growth of Monzo bank:

➤ Growth in branches:

Without the need for actual branch sites, it is confident in its ability to provide efficient, friendly, and timely service. The money it saves by not operating expensive branch networks may be reinvested in improving its services and introducing new features that respond to its clients' individual needs (Monzo Help - Why Monzo Doesn't Have Branches, n.d.)

➤ Growth in customers:

The total number of customers in the Financial year 2021 was 4.8 m, which increased to 5.8 million in the financial year 2022 and then in the financial year 2023 it reached 7.5 million which was a hike of 27.6% as compared to the previous year's growth of 20.8%(Monzo Bank, 2022) and (Lanyon, 2023)

➤ Income trend:

The losses for FY2022 totaled £119.0 million, a 2% rise over the previous fiscal year (FY2021). However, total losses were reduced by 9% from the prior number of £131.1 million (Monzo Bank, 2022). Formally, Monzo recorded a loss of £116.3 million for the fiscal year ending March 2023, a 2% drop from the previous fiscal year ending March 2022 (Lanyon, 2023).

2.2.6. Growth of N26:

➤ Customers

In the year 2018 the total number of customers across 24 countries was 2 million which reached 8 million customers up to the year 2022.

➤ Branches

N26, a digital bank with no expensive branch network or antiquated technology, was a pioneer in developing a cloud-based banking platform. This approach has resulted in the bank having a highly efficient cost structure (N26, 2023).

➤ Income

N26 Net loss for the year 2020 was €150.7m, which further increased to €172.4m in the financial year 2021 (N26, 2023).

2.2.7. Growth of Commerzbank:

- **Income:** Consolidated profit or loss for the year 2021 is €354m, which increased to €1393m in the year 2022 and then in the year June 2023 it further raises to €1145 (Commerzbank, 2022) and (Commerzbank, 2023).
- **Branches:** By the year 2022, the bank will have 450 branches in Germany and 412 worldwide branches (Statista, 2023). From the original 1,000 branches, 450 remained in operation by mid-2022, demonstrating that it completed the reduction specified in its strategy ahead of schedule. (Commerzbank, 2022). Approximately 50 additional branches will be closed, while over 100 will be modernized, with an increase in digital consumer interaction points. (Commerzbank, 2022). The number of branches in Germany was lowered to around 450 the previous year, and it is expected that the aim of 400 branches will be met in 2023. The advising center, which has 12 locations, will service around 8 million branch consumers (Commerzbank, 2022). Foreign branches in operation 16, Representative offices 26, Significant Group firms in other countries 4, Domestic branches in private customer business 450, Foreign branches 412. In the year 2022, the details of branches are as follows: Foreign branches in operation 16, Representative offices 26, Significant Group firms in other countries 4, Domestic branches in private customer business 450, Foreign branches 412(Commerzbank, 2022). The operative foreign branches are in Amsterdam, Beijing, Brno (office), Hong Kong, London, Luxembourg, Madrid, Milan, New York, Paris, Prague, Shanghai, Singapore, Tokyo, Vienna, and Zurich (Commerzbank, 2023).
- **Customers:** Over 18.8 million individual and small company customers are served by Commerzbank, as are over 70,000 corporate clients, multinational corporations, financial service providers, and institutional clients (Ritschel, 2022).

The above literature review chapters from 2.2.4 to 2.2.7 will assist to answer RQ.2

3. Research Methodology

The key objective of the third chapter is to lay out the research technique while also providing insights into the underlying concepts of the methodologies used to fulfill the research objectives. The method utilized to answer research questions is referred to as research methodology. The complexity of the research questions influences methodological selection (Gould & Kolb, 1964).

Typically, research entails gathering information and data in order to evaluate research questions. Once the data has been found, numerous approaches derived from data sources are used in the process. This data analysis aims to evaluate the outcomes (Taylor et al., 2011). The following

sections describe the research design, methods, data sources, and analysis used to achieve the research goal.

3.1. Research Design:

According to Saunders, the research design is Qualitative, Quantitative or Mix research designs. In this research to accumulate pieces of information on establishment and growth based on SWOT analysis, a Qualitative research design is used. The Quantitative research design is used to compare the financial statements of Revolut Bank UAB with its competitors.

3.2. Research Methods

Quantitative Research method: Numbers and mathematical activities are involved. Typically, they are concerned with the collecting and analysis of numerical data. Frequently used for hypothesis testing and quantifying correlations between variables (Aleksandras Melnikovas, 2018).

Qualitative Research method: Involves gathering descriptive, non-numerical data. Emphasize comprehension of the context and significance of occurrences. Frequently used to investigate complicated social and behavioral problems (Aleksandras Melnikovas, 2018).

Mono-Method: Only one type of research approach is used, either quantitative or qualitative. Appropriate when a single approach may properly meet the study issue or aims. When there is a clear preference for either quantitative or qualitative data, this method is useful (Aleksandras Melnikovas, 2018).

Multi-Method: In a research study, this entails using both qualitative and quantitative methods. In contrast to mixed approaches, one of these methods is regarded as fundamental, while the other is auxiliary or additional. This method enables researchers to acquire complementary insights from many forms of data (Aleksandras Melnikovas, 2018).

The choice of research methods and approaches is determined by the nature of the research question, the aims of the study, and the type of data required to properly address the research topic. Researchers can choose the approach or combination of methodologies that best fit their study objectives and constraints. (Aleksandras Melnikovas, 2018)

In this research, the best way to get the answers to the research questions is to use a multi-method, which is a mixture of qualitative and quantitative methods.

The main focus of this thesis is to let consumers and Investors know about the trends of income and expenses, assets and liabilities, and cash balances of the year June 2022 as compared to financial year 2021 and its competitors, triggering consumers' decision to use services and banking facility,

while for investors to know Investment opportunity for which it is essential to carry out analysis of Comparative Financial Statements to derive trends of continuous increase, decrease or fluctuation in its various trends of items present in income statement, balance sheet and cash flow statement. To derive assistance for the above, the quantitative method of approach will suit the best.

The other most important analysis of this thesis is of Common size financial statement over where the percentage of expenses and income as compared to its net operating income, assets and liabilities in contrast to its total assets and different contributors of cash balances by taking operating cash balances as the base will be calculated, which will trigger to conclude on various important proportions, which may assist for managerial and investment decisions. A quantitative method will be followed to collect data and to calculate and analyze various proportions for results useful to managers and Investors.

An organization's growth and establishment before analyzing its income statement is of utmost necessity as an investor and a customer can't decide just based on its financial statements. Establishment and details of growth build a base of faith among investors and customers, which will be done by analyzing content already available from reliable sources. Here qualitative method will be used to derive answers of establishment, growth in the form of the number of branches, customers' rise or decline in profit and to draw a comparative study on its competitor's customers, profit and branches, to know where Revolut bank UAB stands as compared to its benchmarks.

3.3. Methods of collecting data

The researcher must make an important decision about the type of data to be collected for the study, which defines the technique of data collection. Primary data collecting entails the original acquisition of data, whereas secondary data collection entails largely synthesizing existing data (Kothari, 1990).

Primary Data: Primary data in experimental research is often obtained through experiments. However, in descriptive research, such as surveys (which might be sample surveys or census surveys), primary data can be gathered using a variety of methods, including direct engagement with respondents via personal interviews. There are several methods for collecting primary data, particularly in surveys and descriptive research, such as the observation method, the interview method, the use of questionnaires, the use of schedules, and various other methods such as warranty cards, distributor audits, pantry audits, consumer panels, the use of mechanical devices, employing projective techniques (Kothari, 1990).

Secondary Data: Secondary data is information that has previously been acquired and processed by another party. This type of information might be publicized or unpublished. Published data are typically available through a variety of sources, including (a) central, state, or local government

publications, (b) publications from foreign governments or international organizations and their subsidiaries, (c) technical and trade journals, (d) books, magazines, and newspapers, (e) reports and publications from various associations related to business, industry, banks, stock exchanges, and so on, and (f) reports authored by researchers, universities, and other published sources of information (Kothari, 1990).

Unpublished data, on the other hand, comes in a variety of forms, including diaries, letters, unpublished biographies, and autobiographies. Scholars, academics, trade groups, labor bureaus, and other public or private individuals and organizations may also have access to them (Kothari, 1990).

This research will use a collection of secondary data to fulfill the research objectives. The research objective is to know Revolut Bank UAB's establishment there is a need for data that is already available in the form of qualitative content, in case to acquire knowledge on the growth of Revolut Bank UAB's as compared to its competitor's quantitative content are required and to know its position in financial statement analysis through the horizontal and vertical method, past data of financial statements of respective companies are required. So, to carry out the research there is a requirement of secondary data that is already published.

3.4. Validity

Checking the validity of the method used to get the desirable outcome is vital in a research paper (Leung, 2015). The qualitative method used to answer the first and second research questions can provide a reply.

Similarly, the comparative study of financial statements, including profitability measures, is pulled from secondary data to provide an answer to the final stage of analysis between competitors, for which data is obtained from annual reports of the individual banks.

Quantitative data analysis of common-size financial statements of Revolut bank and Commerzbank, whose data were available from respective banks' annual statements, can generate an appropriate response.

Overall, the qualitative and quantitative methodologies utilized for various research questions are capable of meeting the requirements of legitimate sources of information and accurate responses to research questions.

3.5. Methodological Constraints:

The profitability and condition of banks are calculated and concluded based on financial data, but on the other side, their current plans for the future would provide different conclusions about the banks.

The conclusion on the judgment of its competitive growth through horizontal and vertical analysis is based on data already available in the annual reports of the competitive banks and Revolut Bank UAB. While survey and Interview methods to collect data would have changed the conclusion. It means primary data collection methodology would have changed the conclusion, but the most trustable method to look at the financial condition of an organization is an analysis of secondary data already available because individuals may give answers to survey questions or interviews with biased but already existing accounting data can mostly provide a trustworthy fact.

4. Results and Discussions

The results are declared on research questions after evaluation of chapter analysis and considering literature review as basis to form answers for findings. The discussion will be followed after declaration of answers.

4.1. Foundation of Revolut Ltd's Establishment as Revolut Bank UAB

RQ1. What is the foundation of Revolut Ltd's Establishment as Revolut Bank UAB?

The analysis of chapter 2.2.3. can provide answer to this question.

The Base of Revolut Bank UAB was started from the day it was incorporated, which is 6th December 2013 with company No. 8804411 and proposed registered office 60 Arnhem Wharf, Arnhem Place, London, Great Britain, E143RU. This registered office was changed to 1 Canada Square Level 39, 1 Canada Square London E14 5AB on 28 August 2014. However, according to many newspaper articles and Lietuvos Banka's statement, it was founded in 2015. Later in 2017 this bank was able to raise \$66 million in a series B investment round and launched new services in EEA, which include Revolut business, Revolut Premium and crypto trading. 13th December 2018 was one of the very important dates for Revolut Ltd as it was granted Revolut Technologies UAB, a specialized banking license based on the evaluation and recommendation of Lithuanias financial regularities and the board of the bank Lithuania granted Revolut Payments UAB an electronic money institution license. After obtaining this license the Revolut payments UAB started to issue electronic money and abroad a range of payment services, including card payments, direct debits, credit transfers, cash withdrawals, money transmissions, payment initiation, and account information services.

Another important date for Revolut Ltd is 13th December 2021 when it got registration for Revolut Bank UAB, upgraded to include a full banking license, a Lithuanian bank with the registration number 304580906 and the authorization code LB002119, and its official location is Konstitucijos Ave. 21B, 08130 Vilnius, Lithuania, governed and regulated by the Bank of Lithuania and the European Central Bank. Finally, Revolut Payment UAB was merged on 1st July 2022 into Revolut Bank UAB and accordingly, all customers of Revolut Payment UAB were linked to Revolut Bank UAB.

The bank took too long period to get registered as a bank. The important reason behind its registration was the Bank of Lithuania served as a welcoming regulatory authority encouraging innovation, providing one of the shortest licensing processes in the European Union.

4.2. Measures to judge the growth of Revolut Bank UAB Ltd

RQ2. What are the different types of measures to judge the growth of Revolut Bank UAB Ltd?

The different measurements will be in the form of the following:

1. **Different branches and Increase in the number of customers**
2. **SWOT analysis Of Revolut Bank UAB**
3. **Analysis of growth in customers, Income and branches as compared to Challenger banks Monzo Bank Ltd. and N26 as well as traditional bank, Commerzbank.**

The answers to the above research question can be found by analysing chapters 2.2.4 to chapter 2.2.7.

4.2.1. Branches and customers of Revolut Bank UAB

- **Branches:** There are registered branches in the EU but no physical branches. It operates through the mobile app or web-app chat.
- **Customers:**

Table 1: Revolut Bank UAB total customers

Year	2016	2019	2020	2022	June 2023
Total number of customers	100000	10 million	14.5 million	25 million	30 million

The table above gives a clear indication of growth in customers in such a short period which increased from 100,000 customers in 2016 to 10 million in the year 2019, 100 times what it had in the year 2016, after this the growth reached 14.5 million in the year 2020 further escalated to 25 million in the year 2022 and in June 2023 it reached to 30 million. Mostly after the year 2019, the growth ranges between 4.5 million to 5million.

4.2.2. SWOT analysis Of Revolut Bank UAB

Figure 1: SWOT of Revolut Bank UAB

➤ **Strengths:**

Escalating trend of customers: The data from table.1 provides a clear indication of a continuously rising number of customers over the years with a higher speed initially from the year 2016 to the year 2019 the growth is in multiple of 10 and then it increases mostly in the range of 4.5 million customers to 5 million customers.

Figure 2: Total number of customers (Sources Table 1)

Increasing monthly transactions: Escalating trend of customers: The data from table.1 provides a clear indication of a continuously rising number of customers over the years with a higher speed initially from the year 2016 to the year 2019 the growth is in multiple of 10 and then it increases mostly in the range of 4.5 million customers to 5 million customers. It's fantastic to learn that the number of transactions performed by customers has increased! A jump from 350 million transactions in November 2022 to 400 million transactions in November 2023 is a significant increase. Depending on the context, this could indicate increasing client interaction or a bigger customer base.

The expansion of its reach and Innovative Offerings: It is known for its money transfer and currency conversion services, which are expanding rapidly. They currently onboard around one million new subscribers each month, increasing their global user base. Over 30 million retail consumers globally now have access to a diversified range of innovative Revolut products, including peer-to-peer payments, Saving Vaults, 18 distinct account types, and holiday reservation choices. It is crucial to note that these services are subject to specified conditions and limitations.

Tech-driven approach: The Revolut Bank UAB stands forefront of applying new technology to successfully tackle the longstanding difficulties that have traditionally been related to the banking business. In doing so, they provide a comprehensive and diverse variety of financial services geared to satisfy modern clients' complicated and ever-changing needs.

The Incredible Funding Journey of Revolut: Creating a Global Financial Super App:

Revolut's funding trend demonstrates a remarkable evolution: in 2018, they raised \$250 million in their Series C round, followed by an astonishing \$580 million in their Series D round in 2020. They achieved new heights in 2021 when they raised \$800 million in Series E funding. All of this funding is aimed at accomplishing their objective of developing the world's first global financial super-app.

Storonsky's Defiance and Revolut's Financial Strategy:

Storonsky's remarks reflect a general trend in the European fintech sector, where companies are shifting their strategies to favor profitability over quick expansion, recognizing the mounting difficulties in attracting new financing. However, it's important to note that Storonsky flatly denied speculations that Revolut had a two-year financial runway, claiming that the fintech startup isn't under any urgent pressure to seek further funding. This resilience demonstrates their belief in the long-term viability of their existing financial situation.

Financial Resilience and Revenue Generation:

One of the organization's most notable characteristics is its capacity to continually earn interest revenue utilizing the effective interest method, with numbers indicating significant growth at 1298, 40386, and 137490. This financial stability is bolstered further by their ability to retain positive net interest income, as evidenced by the statistics -12525, 27,867, and 137459.

➤ **Weaknesses:**

Security Vulnerability and Financial Loss as a Result of Payment System Flaw:

If hostile actors continue to exploit the fault in Revolut's payment system, a serious future weakness and security risk may occur. According to Isaacs' 2023 assessment, the breach resulted in a loss of more than \$20 million over several months, indicating a risk coming from discrepancies in Revolut's payment processes between the United States and Europe.

The problem largely included transactions that were first refused but later mishandled, drawing on Revolut's resources. Notably, the stolen cash was pulled from Revolut's financial reservoir rather than consumer contributions. Even though around \$23 million was recovered, Revolut suffered a net loss of approximately \$20 million, according to Isaacs' assessment.

➤ **Opportunities:**

Strategic Vision of Revolut: Tailored Consumer Finance

Revolut's unrelenting dedication to implementing its comprehensive strategy plan represents a once-in-a-lifetime chance. The cornerstone of this strategy is the availability of a diverse range of consumer credit choices throughout all European Union markets. The significant emphasis on adaptation, adapting services to the individual demands and tastes of each local market, makes this an attractive potential. This approach portrays Revolut as more than just a financial institution that operates throughout the EU, but as one that understands and responds to the unique financial needs of each region.

The actual opportunity resides in this strategy's connection with Revolut's objective to provide a more personalized and relevant financial experience to its diversified user base across the European Union. Revolut can deepen its presence, create deeper client relationships, and perhaps lead the way in offering new and tailored financial solutions in the EU by catering to the different financial needs of each market.

Expansion into the Swiss Banking Market on a Strategic Basis

The pursuit of a Swiss Representative Office license by Revolut Bank UAB from FINMA, Switzerland's regulatory authorities, represents a significant possibility. The goal is to obtain authorization to provide financial services to Swiss clients. Revolut Ltd can shift its existing client base in Switzerland to the bank following the successful issuance of this license by FINMA, allowing for a seamless and controlled transfer of services.

Furthermore, the Representative Office is viewed as a strategic asset. Its principal responsibility will be to promote the bank's services in Switzerland, opening the way for increased visibility and involvement in the Swiss market. Furthermore, direct registration of new Swiss clients with the bank

improves accessibility and solidifies the groundwork for long-term growth and service expansion in the Swiss banking scene. This attempt opens the door to expanded market reach and a more substantial presence in the Swiss financial sector.

➤ **Threats:**

Recurring Cybersecurity Challenges: Vulnerabilities Used to Steal Data and Money:

The current event involving Revolut highlights the pervasive threat of cyberattacks, emphasizing bad actors' readiness to exploit any weakness for the goal of data and financial losses. This instance demonstrates the idea that if a weakness exists, it can become a target.

These cyberattacks frequently originate at the point of the human-computer interface. In the case of Revolut, the breach was caused by the financial exploitation of a procedural flaw. Attacks on banks and financial organizations, on the other hand, often cover a broader range of activities, comprising a combination of human activities, operational processes, and computer systems.

Statistica Statistics and the DBIR study both confirm the serious threat that financial institutions (FIs) confront, particularly phishing efforts. These findings highlight the vital link between stolen credentials and data breaches, which poses a continuing and serious danger to the financial sector's cybersecurity.

4.2.3. Comparative Evaluation of customers, Income and branches

Evaluation of growth in customers, Income and branches as compared to Challenger banks Monzo Bank Ltd. and N26 as well as traditional bank, Commerzbank.

➤ **Growth in customers**

Table 2: Growth in customers in Revolut Bank UAB, Monzo Bank, N26, Commerzbank.

Year→ Banks↓	2016	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	June. 2023
Revolut bank UAB	100000		10 million	14.5		25 million	30millions
Monzo bank					4.8 million	5.8 million	7.5million

N26		2 million				8 million	
Commerzbank						18.87million	

This is from the analysis of the growth of all the banks in Chapter 3.4.2

Revolut Bank UAB - They had 100,000 customers in 2016, and by 2018, their customer base had grown to 10 million. This is a huge increase.

- The number of consumers increased to 14.5 million in 2019, 25 million in 2021, and 30 million in June 2023.

- Over the years, Revolut Bank UAB has seen significant and continuous customer growth.

Monzo Bank: Monzo Bank had no data for 2016 or 2017, however, they had 4.8 million customers in 2018.

- By 2019, its customer base had grown to 5.8 million, representing a 20.83% rise.

- Monzo's growth appears to be slower than that of Revolut Bank UAB.

N26: -N26 had no data for 2016, 2018, or 2020, yet they had 2 million customers in 2019. Their customer base has grown to 8 million, suggesting considerable expansion. However, because of the missing data points, determining the precise growth rate for N26 is difficult.

Commerzbank: - Commerzbank did not have data for 2016, 2018, 2019, or 2021, however, they had 18.87 million customers in 2020.

➤ **Growth in Branches:**

Revolut Bank UAB has a virtual presence across the EU, offering its services only through mobile and web apps, with no physical locations.

Monzo Bank, on the other hand, intends to streamline its operations by foregoing the costly branch network in favor of focusing on improving its services and introducing new features to better serve its clients.

By functioning as a digital bank, N26 maintains a highly efficient cost structure by avoiding the overhead associated with traditional branch networks.

Commerzbank, on the other hand, is a traditional bank with a significant global presence, with between 800 to 1000 physical branches worldwide. However, it is in the process of carefully lowering the number of branches while increasing digital client connection points.

➤ **Growth in Income**

Table 3: Growth in Income Revolut Bank UAB, Monzo Bank, N26, Commerzbank

Year→	2020	2021	2022	2023
Revolut bank UAB	-	€43.254 million	€23.970 million	€27.000million
Monzo bank	-	£-131.1 million (€-150.738 million)	£-119.0 million (loss decrease by 9%) (€-136.873 million)	£-116.3 million (2% drop in loss) (-174.45)
N26	€-150.7million loss	€-172.4million (14.40% rise in loss)	-	-
Commerzbank	-	€354million	€1393million	€1145million

This is from the analysis of the growth of all the banks in Chapters 2.2.4 and 2.2.7 and Appendix 3.

According to the data above, Commerzbank is the largest income earner among banks, owing to its long-established position and global reach. Revolut Bank UAB, on the other hand, shows a favorable trend in net income, expanding from €43.254 million to €23.970 million and subsequently to €27.000 million. This exceeds Monzo's income, which has been continually negative, ranging between €-150.738 million, €-136.873 million, and €-174.45 million.

When comparing Revolut Bank UAB's revenues to N26's, it is clear that N26's losses increased from €-150.7 million to €-172.4 million in 2021. However, It is important to note that Revolut's income is steadily increasing, in contrast to N26's losses.

In the instance of Commerzbank, the income has increase by 233.72% from €354 million in 2021 to €1393 million in 2022. However, it falls to €1145 million in 2023, representing a 19.02% decrease from the previous year. Nonetheless, Revolut's income continues to grow at a fluctuating rate in comparison to the benchmark banks, albeit being lower than Commerzbank's income.

4.3. Analysis of comparative financial statements

RQ3. What is the final stage of analysis of comparative financial statements as on 31st December of 2021, 2022 and 30th June 2023?

The Comparative analysis will be as follows:

1. Comparative financial statements analysis of Revolut Bank UAB will be for three consecutive years.
2. Comparative analysis of financial statements key figures of Monzo Bank Ltd, N26 and Commerzbank and then comparison of it with Revolut Bank UAB financial statements. Knowing the position of the financial statements of Revolut Bank UAB as compared to its competitors will help Revolut Bank UAB to know its position as well as investors to make decisions on Investment.

4.3.1. Analysis of Comparative financial statements (Revolut Bank UAB)

➤ Income statement:

- Income Statement FY2021-2022 and FY2022-2023: the FY ends in December every year except for the year 2023 it is a comparison with an interim financial statement which ends on 30th June. The analysis of the Income statement shows that Interest income increased by 3011.40% from FY 2021-2022 and then the rise decreased by 240.44% in FY 2023 as compared to FY 2022.
- Interest expenses declined by 9.43% in the year 2022 as compared to the year 2021, which shows an unexpected decline of 99.75%.
- Overall Net income shows an increase to 322.49% in the year 2022 as compared to the year 2021. The increase further rises by 393.27% in the year 2023 and then in the year 2022.
- Fees and commission income rose by 79.07% in the year 2022 in comparison to the previous year, showing a decline in the next year by 32.95% as compared to the financial year 2022.
- Fees and commission expenses show a fluctuating trend in the ye2021-2023 with an increase of 16.39% in the year 2022 and then a decline of 33.71% in the year 2023.
- Net Fee and Commission Income grew by 179,887 Euros (an increase of 119.53%) from 150,489 Euros in December 2021 to 330,376 Euros in December 2022. However, it fell to 222,386 Euros in June 2023, a decline of 107,990 Euros (a 32.69% drop).
- Net Gains and Losses on Financial Items increased by 14,008 Euros (a -193.32% decline) from -7,246 Euros in December 2021 to 6,762 Euros in December 2022. By June 2023, they had risen to 28,438 Euros, representing a shift of 21,676 Euros (a 320.56% increase).
- Credit Loss Expense on Financial Assets increased by -13,370 Euros (a 163.07 percent rise) from -8,199 Euros in December 2021 to -21,569 Euros in December 2022. It was -21,794 Euros in June 2023, a change of -225 Euros (a percentage rise of 1.04%).
- The exchange difference gain (loss) in December 2021 was 0 Euros, and it stayed at 0 Euros in December 2022, but it was -8,503 Euros in June 2023.
- Provisions were 0 Euros in December 2021 and 2022 but were -54 Euros in June 2023.

- Other Operating Income grew by 31,838 Euros (221.51%) from 14,373 Euros in December 2021 to 46,211 Euros in December 2022. However, it became 0 Euros in June 2023, representing a reduction of 46,211 Euros (a decrease of 100.00%).
- Net Operating Income increased by 252,755 Euros (an increase of 184.64%) from 136,892 Euros in December 2021 to 389,647 Euros in December 2022. However, it fell to 357,932 Euros in June 2023, a drop of 31,715 Euros (a drop of 8.14%).
- Personnel Expenses increased by -16,078 Euros (249.39%) from -6,447 Euros in December 2021 to -22,525 Euros in December 2022. They were 21,750 Euros in June 2023, an increase of 44,275 Euros (a 196.56% reduction).
- Depreciation and Amortization increased by -181 Euros (75.12%) from -213 Euros in December 2021 to -373 Euros in December 2022. By June 2023, they had grown to 181 Euros, a 554 Euro rise (a 148.53% decline).
- Other Operating Expenses increased by -259,356 Euros (335.64%) from -77,226 Euros in December 2021 to -336,582 Euros in December 2022. They were 301,497 Euros in June 2023, a change of 638,079 Euros (a drop of 189.58%).
- Total Operating Expenses increased by -275,594 Euros from -83,886 Euros in December 2021 to -359,480 Euros in December 2022. They were 323,428 Euros in June 2023, a change of 682,908 Euros.
- Profit Before Tax was 53,006 Euros in December 2021, 30,167 Euros in December 2022, and 34,504 Euros in June 2023.
- Tax expenses fell from -9,357 Euros in December 2021 to -6,612 Euros in December 2022 before rising to 7,504 Euros in June 2023.
- The profit for the year was 43,649 Euros in December 2021, 23,555 Euros in December 2022, and 27,000 Euros in June 2023.

Summary

Net interest income has increased significantly, which is a healthy indicator. The bank should continue to focus on increasing interest income while properly managing interest expenses.

Fees and Commission Income: While fees and commission income increased sharply in December 2022, it fell in June 2023. The bank should investigate the reasons for this reduction and devise methods to preserve a consistent income stream in this category.

Gains and Losses on Financial Items: In this area, the bank turned a loss into a profit. This implies better risk management or trading techniques. To achieve consistent profitability, the bank should continue to examine and optimize its financial conditions.

Tax Expenses: A decrease in tax expenses is a good sign. To increase profitability, the bank should maintain efficient tax management techniques.

➤ **Balance sheet**

- The following is a comparative analysis of Revolut Bank UAB's balance sheet for the years ending in December 2021, December 2022, and June 2023:
- **Assets:** Cash and central bank balances climbed from 3,448,265 Euros in December 2021 to 6,921,501 Euros in December 2022 and to 7,577,198 Euros in June 2023. This is a shift of 3,473,236 Euros (a 100.72 percent increase) from 2021 to 2022 and 655,697 Euros (a 9.47 percent increase) from 2022 to 2023.
- Bank payments fell from 115,091 Euros in December 2021 to 8,396 Euros in December 2022, then rose to 11,658 Euros in June 2023. This is a drop of -106,695 Euros (a decrease of 92.70%) from 2021 to 2022 and an increase of 3,262 Euros (a 38.85% increase) from 2022 to 2023.
- Other financial institutions' dues declined dramatically from 129,484 Euros in December 2021 to 1,358 Euros in December 2022, with no such due in June 2023. This represents a -128,126 Euro (98.95% decline) from 2021 to 2022 and a 100% decrease from 2022 to 2023.
- At amortized cost, debt securities/debt instruments climbed from 1,015,081 Euros in December 2021 to 1,110,256 Euros in December 2022, and then to 1,854,403 Euros in June 2023. This represents a shift of 95,175 Euros (a 9.38 percent increase) from 2021 to 2022 and 744,147 Euros (a 67.02 percent increase) from 2022 to 2023.
- Loans and illegal overdrafts climbed significantly from 23,548 Euros in December 2021 to 230,837 Euros in December 2022 and 4,18,776 Euros in June 2023. This indicates an increase of 207,289 Euros (880.28%) from 2021 to 2022 and an increase of 1,87,939 Euros (81.42%) from 2022 to 2023.
- Other assets grew from 123,169 Euros in December 2021 to 486,599 Euros in December 2022 and 513,818 Euros in June 2023. This is a shift of 363,430 Euros (a 295.07% increase) from 2021 to 2022 and 27,219 Euros (a 5.59% increase) from 2022 to 2023.
- Total assets grew from 4,878,397 Euros in December 2021 to 8,779,475 Euros in December 2022, then to 10,379,617 Euros in June 2023. This indicates a change of 3,901,078 Euros (a 79.97% rise) from 2021 to 2022 and 1,600,442 Euros (an 18.23% increase) from 2022 to 2023.
- **Liabilities:** Derivatives fell from 8,284 Euros in December 2021 to 2,800 Euros in December 2022 and 194 Euros in June 2023. This represents a decline of -5,484 Euros (66.20%) from 2021 to 2022 and a decrease of -2,606 Euros (93.07%) from 2022 to 2023.
- Due to Customers increased the value of the company from 4,544,087 Euros in December 2021 to 8,083,838 Euros in December 2022, and then to 9,783,673 Euros in June 2023. This is a change of 3,539,751 Euros (a 77.90% increase) from 2021 to 2022 and a change of 1,699,835 Euros (a 21.03%) from 2022 to 2023.
- Due to other financial institutions grew from 24,155 Euros in December 2021 to 191,561 Euros in December 2022, with no such liabilities in June 2023. This represents a 167,406 Euro change (a 693.05 percent increase) from 2021 to 2022 and a 100% drop from 2022 to 2023.

- Other liabilities grew from 48,964 Euros in December 2021 to 104,416 Euros in December 2022 and 111,204 Euros in June 2023. This represents a shift of 55,452 Euros (a 113.25% increase) from 2021 to 2022 and 6,788 Euros (a 6.50% increase) from 2022 to 2023.
- Other liabilities climbed from 48,964 Euros in December 2021 to 104,416 Euros in December 2022 and 111,204 Euros in June 2023. This represents a shift of 55,452 Euros (a 113.25% increase) from 2021 to 2022 and 6,788 Euros (a 6.50% increase) from 2022 to 2023.
- Total liabilities rose from 4,625,522 Euros in December 2021 to 8,382,718 Euros in December 2022, then to 9,896,598 Euros in June 2023. This represents a shift of 3,757,196 Euros (an 81.23 % increase) from 2021 to 2022 and 1,513,880 Euros (an 18.06% increase) from 2022 to 2023.
- Equity: From December 2021 to June 2023, the share capital remained steady at 36,815 Euros.
- The reserve capital increased from 169,600 Euros in December 2021 to 279,008 Euros in December 2022, with no reserve capital in June 2023. This is a shift of 109,408 Euros (a 64.51 percent increase) from 2021 to 2022 and a 100% decrease from 2022 to 2023.
- Retained earnings grew from 44,451 Euros in December 2021 to 75,071 Euros in December 2022, then to 98,317 Euros in June 2023. This is a shift of 30,620 Euros (a 68.88% increase) from 2021 to 2022 and 23,246 Euros (a 30.97% increase) from 2022 to 2023.
- Other reserves grew from 2,009 Euros in December 2021 to 5,863 Euros in December 2022 and 347,887 Euros in June 2023. This represents a shift of 3,854 Euros (a 191.84% increase) from 2021 to 2022 and 342,024 Euros (a 5833.60% increase) from 2022 to 2023.
- Total equity increased from 252,875 Euros in December to 252,875 Euros now.

Summary

Asset Growth: The significant increase in total assets is encouraging. To sustain this expansion, the bank needs to ensure responsible asset management, including lending, investments, and asset quality.

Customer liability is a significant liability component. The bank should continue to recruit and retain customer deposits while also keeping the reliability of its funding sources in mind.

Equity: Increased equity is a good thing. To fund additional expansion and maintain a high capital adequacy ratio, the bank might explore leveraging its improved equity base.

➤ **Statement of changes in Equity**

Analysis of the major indicators for Revolut Bank UAB based on the statement of changes in equity for the fiscal year ended December 31, 2022:

- Share Capital: From the beginning of the year to the conclusion of the year, the share capital remained constant at €36,815.
- Reserve Capital: Reserve capital increased dramatically by €109,408, representing a 64.51% rise. The increase in reserve capital suggests that more funds were allocated to this capital category this year.

- **Legal Reserve:** The legal reserve increased by €2,527, representing a 287.81% gain. This implies that during the year, a portion of the profit was allotted to the legal reserve.
- **Translation Reserve:** Throughout the year, the translation reserve remained stable at €15.00.
- **Fair Value Reserve:** Throughout the year, the fair value reserve remained steady at €0.00.
- **Retained Earnings:** Retained earnings increased by €30,620, representing a 68.88% rise.
- This huge increase in retained earnings shows that the bank kept a sizable share of its profits.
- **Other Reserves** increased by €912, showing that funds were allocated or transferred to this reserve category during the year.
- **Total Equity:** Revolut Bank UAB's total equity as of December 31, 2022 was €396,757.00. Total equity increased by €143,882 compared to the beginning of the year, representing a 56.90% rise.

Summary

This analysis shows that Revolut Bank UAB increased its reserve capital, legal reserve, retained earnings, and total equity significantly during the year.

These improvements reflect good financial performance and the distribution of profits among equity groups. Furthermore, the bank's share capital remained steady, but other reserves and the translation reserve did not alter much.

➤ **Statement of Cash Flows Statement**

The following is Revolut Bank UAB's comparative cash flow statement, with percentage change, comparing December 2021 and December 2022:

Activities of Operation:

- Profit before tax declined by 22,839 Euros, representing a 43.09% fall.
- Interest income increased significantly, with a positive change of 39,088 Euros, or a percentage change of 3,011.40%.
- Interest expenses dropped by 1,304 Euros, representing a 9.43% decrease.
- Financial asset impairment grew significantly by 28,713 Euros, resulting in a 405.09% percentage change.
- Depreciation and amortization expenses climbed by 160 Euros, representing a 75.12% rise.
- Net movements in derivative financial instruments declined by 1,755 Euros, representing a - 693.68% percentage change.
- Net loan and unauthorised overdraft movements climbed by 207,740 Euros, reflecting a percentage change of 1,037.51%.
- The net change in financial assets was 920,629 Euros, resulting in a percentage change of - 90.66%.

- Change in other operational assets declined by 308,766 Euros, representing a -593.44% percentage change.
- Change in other operational liabilities grew by 201,227 Euros, representing a 572.69% percentage change.
- Deposits increased by a large amount of 1,784,873 Euros, resulting in a percentage change of 101.71%.
- Gain or loss from exchange differences dropped by 41,631 Euros, representing a -999.54% percentage change.
- Share-based payments to employees declined by 331 Euros, representing a -26.63% percentage change.
- Provision for deferred assets grew by 2,028 Euros, representing an 186.91% rise.
- The amount of income tax paid increased by 18,609 Euros, reflecting a percentage rise of 1,524.08%.
- Interest paid increased by 1,276 Euros, representing a -9.21% percentage change.
- The amount of interest received increased by 38,187 Euros, resulting in a percentage change of 3,127.52%.
- Total operating cash flows increased by 2,330,974 Euros, resulting in a 310.25% percentage rise.

Investing Activities:

- Property and equipment purchases were reduced by 2 Euros, representing a 12.50% drop.

Financing Activities:

- The proceeds from the formation of reserve capital fell by 40,600 Euros, representing a -25.44% loss.
- The principal payments on lease liabilities grew by 181 Euros, resulting in a 107.74% percentage rise.
- Total cash flows from financial activities declined by 40,781 Euros, representing a -25.58% percentage reduction.
- Net cash and cash equivalents increase:
- The net increase in cash and cash equivalents was 2,290,191 Euros, representing a 251.46% percentage change.
- The net foreign exchange difference increased by 41,641 Euros, representing a -1,000.99% percentage change.
- Cash and cash equivalents:
- Cash and cash equivalents increased by 906,583 Euros at the start of the year (1 January), representing a 32.54% gain.
- Cash and cash equivalents climbed by 3,238,415 Euros at the end of the year (31 December), representing an 87.69% rise.

Operating Activities: The significant increase in cash flows from operating activities is a positive sign that the bank can produce cash from its core operations. The bank should continue to improve operational efficiency while maintaining good working capital management.

Activities of Financing:

- The bank raised capital through reserve capital. It should examine the requirement for extra money and look into the most cost-effective finance options.

Summary

Despite hurdles such as a major drop in profitability, financial asset impairment, and foreign exchange losses, the company was able to enhance its cash flow from operations and raise its cash and cash equivalents. This suggests that the organization has taken initiatives to improve operational efficiency and liquidity. The foreign exchange discrepancy, on the other hand, had a significant negative influence on the overall financial picture.

➤ Profitability Ratios: Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE):

- ROE fell from 17.10% in December 2021 to 6.04% in December 2022 and 5.59% in June 2023. This suggests that the company's ability to make profits relative to shareholders' equity is deteriorating.
- ROA has also dropped from 0.89% in December 2021 to 0.27% in December 2022, and then to 0.26% in June 2023. This indicates a downward tendency in the company's efficiency in generating earnings from its assets.
- Declining ROE and ROA, indicates the need for more efficiency in asset usage and cost management. To increase profitability, the bank should focus on enhancing asset quality, lowering operational expenses, and growing income.
- Over the stated periods, these trends imply a reduction in profitability and efficiency. It is critical that the organization analyze the factors behind these decreases and execute plans to enhance its financial performance.

4.3.2. Analysis of Comparative Financial Statements (Revolut Bank UAB with its Competitors)

➤ Income Statements

Table 4: comparative income statement

Comparative Income statement	Revolut bank UAB	Revolut bank UAB	Monzo Bank	Comerzbank	Comerzbank
Particulars	% change (2022-2023)				
Interest income	3011.40	240.44	57.87	42.16	-20.42
Interest expense	-9.43	-99.75	138.30	60.11	7.05
Net interest income	322.49	393.27	52.25	33.20	-36.89
Fee and commission income	79.07	-32.95	91.06	-1.43	-50.29
Fee and commission expense	16.39	-33.71	83.29	4.17	-51.26
Net fee and commission income	119.53	-32.69	93.34	-2.44	-50.10
Net operating income	184.64	-8.14	81.44	8.95	-41.32
Total operating expense	328.53	-189.97	19.88	-15.37	-50.38
Total comprehensive profit or loss for the year, net of tax	-44.58	12.64	-9.20	233.72	-19.02

Sources: Annual reports and Appendix 3

Interest Income:

- Interest income at Revolut Bank UAB increased significantly (3011.40%), but increase in 2023 is at a declining rate by 240.44% suggesting significant growth in this revenue source.

- Monzo Bank's interest income increased significantly by 57.87% as compared to year 2021, although not as much as Revolut's.
- In contrast, Commerzbank's interest income decreased (42.16%), and then declined (-20.42%) showing a reduction in this revenue source.
- Revolut Bank saw an outstanding growth in interest income, while Monzo Bank saw a substantial gain. Commerzbank, on the other hand, reported a reduction in interest income.

Interest Expense:

- Revolut Bank UAB saw a little drop in interest expense (-9.43%), and then reduced dramatically (-99.75%), indicating significant interest cost reduction.
- In contrast Monzo Bank's interest expenditure increase by 138.30% .
- On the other hand, Commerzbank's interest expenses increased (60.11%), and further increased at a dropping rate by 7.05% in the year 2023.
- Revolut Bank effectively managed its interest expense to a dramatic reduction; however, Monzo Bank had a significant increase. Interest expenses increased at Commerzbank as well.

Income from net interest:

- Revolut Bank UAB's net interest income increased significantly (322.49%) and then by 393.49. This gain is mostly due to a significant increase in interest revenue, which offset a modest drop in interest expenses.
- Monzo Bank's net interest income increased by (52.25%), owing mostly to an increase in interest income and a drop in interest expense.
- Commerzbank's net interest income shows increase (33.20%), and then decreased significantly (-36.89%), showing mostly to a reduction in interest income.
- Revolut Bank reported a significant increase in net interest income, indicating excellent interest revenue growth. Monzo Bank also saw a large boost. However, net interest income at Commerzbank fell significantly.

Fee and commission income:

- Revolut bank shows Fees and commission income increased initially by 79.07% and then declined (-32.95%).
- Monzo bank shows increase in fees and commission income by 91.06%
- Commerzbank fees and commission income declines dramatically from -1.43% to -50.29%
- Both Revolut Bank and Commerzbank reported a decline in fee and commission income, while Monzo Bank reporting an increase.

Fee and Commission Expenses:

- Revolut bank shows decline in fees and commission expense by 16.39% and then by -33.71.
- While Monzo Bank highlights significant increase by 83.29%.

- In contrast Commerzbank shows increase in commission expense by 4.17%, and then dramatic decline by 51.26%.
- Both Revolut Bank and Commerzbank kept their fee and commission expenses under control. This cost increased significantly for Monzo Bank.

Net Fee and Commission Income:

- Revolut Bank Highlights escalating increase in Net fees and commission income (119%) and then the increase declined by (32.69%)
- In case of Monzo Bank the net fee and commission income increased by 93.34%.
- Commerzbank shows a dramatic decline by -2.44, and then by -50.10% in the year 2023
- Revolut Bank shows fluctuating value from high increase to decline, while Monzo shows increase in net fee and commission income. Commerzbank, on the other hand, saw a considerable drop.

Net Operating Income:

- Revolut Bank Shows escalating increase in Net operating income (184.64%), and then drops by (-8.14).
- Monzo bank shows increase in net operating income by 81.44%.
- Commerzbank highlights increase in net operating income by 8.95% and then escalating decline (-41.32%).
- Revolut Bank's net operating income increases dramatically and then drops significantly, showing big fluctuation in revenue growth. While, Monzo Banks net operating income increases as compared to the year 2021. Commerzbank reported a lesser increase in net operating income, and then higher drop. This indicates Revolut Bank and Commerzbank, both had a fluctuation net operating income than the other two banks.

Total Operating Expense:

- Revolut Banks total operating expense rose up by 328,53% and then declined (-189.97%), indicating good step by management to reduce operating expenses.
- Monzo Bank shows increase in total operating expenses (19.88%) as compared to previous year.
- Commerzbank also shows decline in total operating expenses by -15.37% to decline by -50,38%.
- Revolut Bank's total and Commerzbank are able to reduce their total operating expenses, which is an effective cost-cutting approach. While, Monzo Bank likewise claimed an increase.

Total Compounded Profit/Loss:

- Revolut Bank's total comprehensive profit decreased drastically (-44.58%), and then increases by 12.64% while Monzo Bank's total comprehensive loss decreased (-9.20%). The entire comprehensive profit of Commerzbank fell rose up significantaly (233.72%), and then dropped by -19.02%.

- Revolut is able to control the drop in profit and has an increase in the next year, while Monzo bank has control on its loss and Commerzbank shows highly fluctuating comprehensive profit.

➤ Balance Sheets

Table 5: consolidated statement of financial position

Comparative statement financial position	Revolut Bank UAB	Revolut Bank UAB	Monzo Bank	Commerzbank	Commerzbank
	% change 2021-2022	% change 2022-23	% change 2021-2022	% change 2021-2022	% change 2022-23
Total assets	79.97	18.23	43.77	2.15	5.06
Liabilities	79.97	18.23	36.63	2.05	5.18
Equity	56.90	21.74	153.39	3.61	3.36

Total Assets:

- Revolut Bank's total assets increased significantly from 2021 to 2022 (79.97% change) and somewhat from 2022 to 2023 (18.23% change). The percentage change in total assets was significant, indicating rapid expansion.
- Monzo Bank's total assets increased significantly from 2021 to 2022 (43.77% change). It showed a significant growth in total assets, albeit at a lesser percentage change than Revolut Bank.
- From 2021 to 2022, Commerzbank's total assets increased by 2.15%, and again by 5.06% from 2022 to 2023. A much smaller percentage change in total assets compared to the other banks, indicating a slower rate of expansion.

Liabilities:

- Revolut Bank's liabilities increased significantly from 2021 to 2022 (79.97% change) and more moderately from 2022 to 2023 (18.23% change). In both times, there was a significant growth in liabilities that was by the increase in total assets. This implies that financial commitments are effectively managed.

- Monzo Bank's liabilities increased significantly from 2021 to 2022 (36.63% change). There is a considerable increase in liabilities, although the percentage change was lower as compared to Revolut Bank, showing that financial responsibilities grew at a slower pace.
- Commerzbank had a relatively lesser growth in liabilities from 2021 to 2022 (2.05% change) and a little larger increase from 2022 to 2023 (5.18% change). A lower percentage change in liabilities, indicating a more cautious approach to accumulating financial commitments.

Equity:

- The equity of Revolut Bank increased dramatically from 2021 to 2022 (56.90% change) and continued to rise at a faster rate from 2022 to 2023 (21.74% change). A spectacular gain in equity surpassed the expansion in total assets. This indicates a high level of capital accumulation and an efficient capital structure.
- Monzo Bank's equity increased even more significantly from 2021 to 2022 (153.39% change). An even greater growth in equity than Revolut Bank. The percentage change in equity was significant, indicating significant capital growth.
- Commerzbank's equity increased as well, albeit at a slower rate from 2021 to 2022 (3.61% change) and then again from 2022 to 2023 (3.36% change). A moderate gain in equity shows even if the percentage change was lower, there was still consistent growth.

Comparative statement of cash flow statement

Table 6: Comparative statement of Cash flow statement

Comparative statement of Cash flow statement	Revolut % change 2021-23	Monzo Bank % change 2021-2022	Commerzbank % change 2021-2022
Net cash flows from operating activities	337.07	-40.03	-206.59
Net cash flows from Investing activities	12.50	355.24	-11.32
Net cash from financing activities	-25.58	127.00	-114.70
Net increase in cash and cash equivalent	251.46	-90.20	123.33
Cash and cash equivalents at beginning of the year	32.54	116.74	-34.52

Cash and cash equivalent at the end of the year	87.69	5.28	51.96
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- Net Cash Flows from Operating Activities: Revolut Bank's net cash flows from operating activities increased by 337.07%, suggesting excellent growth in cash earned from core operations.
- Monzo Bank witnessed a large reduction in net cash flows from operational activities of -40.03%, indicating difficulties in earning cash from its core businesses.
- Commerzbank reported a large reduction in this indicator of -206.59%, indicating a considerable decrease in cash generated from operating activities.

Net Cash Flows from Investing Activities:

- Revolut Bank reported an increase in net cash flows from investing activities of 12.50%, showing a moderate increase in cash generated from investments.
- Monzo Bank witnessed a strong increase in net cash flows from investing operations of 355.24%, indicating a significant influx of cash from investments.
- Commerzbank's net cash flows from investing activities decreased by -11.32%, showing a fall in cash generated from investments.

Net cash generated by financing activities:

- Revolut Bank reported a decline in net cash from financing activities of -25.58%, suggesting a decrease in cash received from financing sources.
- Monzo Bank's net cash from financing activities increased by 127.00%, suggesting a high inflow of cash from financing sources.
- Commerzbank saw a -114.70% fall in net cash from financing activities, indicating a decrease in cash received from financing sources.

Net Cash and Cash Equivalents Increase:

- Revolut Bank reported a strong increase in net cash and cash equivalents of 251.46%, showing considerable expansion in liquidity.
- Monzo Bank's net cash and cash equivalents decreased by -90.20%, indicating a drop in liquidity.
- Commerzbank reported a 123.33% growth in net cash and cash equivalents, indicating improved liquidity.

Changes in Cash and Cash Equivalents at the Start and End of the Year: The changes in cash and cash equivalents at the start and end of the year show the influence of cash flow activities on overall liquidity for each bank.

Summary

- Revolut Bank's cash flows from operating activities and cash and cash equivalents have grown rapidly. It must maintain its current growth rate and analyze its financing options.
- Monzo Bank is struggling to generate cash from core businesses while also sustaining liquidity. It should evaluate operational efficiency as well as funding options.
- Commerzbank has reported large decreases in cash flows from operations and finance. It should concentrate on ways to reverse these trends and improve general financial health.
- The findings highlight the differences in these banks' financial circumstances and strategies, with Revolut Bank seeing growth, Monzo Bank encountering issues, and Commerzbank seeking to improve its financial performance.

➤ **Statement of Changes in Equity**

Revolut Bank UAB

Table 7: Statement of Changes in Equity

Particulars	Share Capital	Reserve capital	Legal reserve	translation reserve	Fair value reserve	other reserves	Total equity	Reserve capital
% change as compared to the start of the year	0	64.51	287.81	300.00	-100.00	59.76	56.90	% change

Monzo Bank

Table 8: Statement of Changes in Equity Monzo Bank

Particulars	Share Capital	Share premium	other reserves	Retained losses	Total equity
% change as compared to the start of the year		85.75	40.25	34.50	153.39

Commerzbank

other reserves

Table 9: Statement of Changes in Equity commerzbank

Particulars	Subscribed capital	capital reserve	retained earnings	Revaluation reserve	Cash flow hedge reserve	Currency translation reserve	Equity attributable to shareholders	Additional equity components	Noncontrolling interest	Equity
% change as compared to the start of the year	0.00	0.00	9.93	419.77	32.95	-17.42	4.53	0.00	-8.92	3.62

Revolut Bank UAB (Revolut):

- Share Capital: The share capital remained steady during the year.
- Reserve Capital: A significant growth in reserve capital of 64.51%, suggesting a strong accumulation of capital reserves.
- Legal Reserve: The legal reserve increased by 287.81%, indicating that large legal reserves were established over the year.
- Translation Reserve: A 300.00% increase in the translation reserve, implying large currency-related adjustments.
- A 100% decline in the fair value reserve indicates that it has been completely depleted.
- Other Reserves: Other reserves increased by 59.76%, indicating growth in other equity components.
- Total equity: Total equity increased by 56.90% as a result of favorable developments in capital and reserves.

Monzo Bank:

- There is no particular percentage change data supplied for share capital.

- Share Premium: The share premium increased by 85.75%, indicating a large capital influx from premium shares.
- Other Reserves: Other reserves increased by 40.25%, reflecting growth in equity components.
- Retained Losses increased by 34.50%, reflecting the impact of losses on equity.
- Total Equity: Total equity increased by 153.39% as a result of increases in share premiums, other reserves, and retained losses.

Commerzbank:

- There is no particular percentage change data for subscribed capital.
- There is no precise percentage change data for the capital reserve.
- Retained Earnings: Retained earnings increased by 9.93%, indicating a positive change in this component.
- Revaluation Reserve: A 419.77% increase in the revaluation reserve, indicating large revaluation changes.
- Cash Flow Hedge Reserve: The cash flow hedge reserve increased by 32.95%, showing favorable increases in this reserve.
- Currency Translation Reserve: A -17.42% reduction in the currency translation reserve, indicating that currency swings hurt equity.
- Equity Attributable to Shareholders: The equity attributable to shareholders increased by 4.53%.
- Additional Equity Components: A drop of -8.92% in additional equity components.
- Noncontrolling Interest: An increase of 3.62% in noncontrolling interest.

➤ **Profitability Ratios ROE and ROA**

Return on Equity:

Table 10: Return on Equity

ROE	2021	2022	2023
Revolut Bank UAB	17.10	6.04	5.59
Monzo Bank	-59.07	-21.17	-
Commerzbank	1.44	4.64	3.64

- Revolut Bank UAB: ROE fell from 17.10% in 2021 to 6.04% in 2022 and 5.59% in 2023, exhibiting a downward trend.

- Monzo Bank: ROE has been continually negative (data for 2023 is missing), indicating ongoing concerns.
- Commerzbank's ROE remained generally constant, rising from 1.44% in 2021 to 4.64% in 2022 before falling slightly to 3.64% in 2023.

ROA (Return on Assets):

Table 11: Return on Assets

ROA	2021	2022	2023
Revolut Bank UAB	0.89	0.27	0.26
Monzo Bank	-3.61	-2.28	-
Commerzbank	0.09	0.30	0.23

- Revolut Bank UAB's ROA fell from 0.89% in 2021 to 0.27% in 2022 and 0.26% in 2023.
- Monzo Bank: ROA has been continually negative (data for 2023 is lacking), showing operational inefficiencies.
- Commerzbank's ROA remained very steady, rising from 0.09% in 2021 to 0.30% in 2022 before falling slightly to 0.23% in 2023.

4.4. Analysis of vertical financial Statements

RQ4. What is the analysis of vertical financial statements of Revolut bank UAB as well as competitors Monzo Bank Ltd, N26 and Commerzbank as on 30th June 2023 indicates regarding the following:

- 1. Proportion of different income and expenses as compared to their Net Operating Income and whether are they able to pay off expenses with income earned after which a comparison of Revolut Bank UAB with its competitors.**
- 2. Proportion of different assets and liabilities as compared to their Total Assets and to measure the adequacy of assets to ensure financial security to customers, and investors, which is further preceded by comparison of Revolut Bank UAB with its competitors.**

The Data was available only for Revolut Bank UAB and Commerzbank, therefore the vertical comparison is restricted to these two banks only. Further, in the absence of cash flow statement and Statement of Changes in equity, in Revolut Bank UAB Annual report, only Income statements and Balance sheets are considered to prepare and analyse vertical Statements.

4.4.1. Comparative Analysis Vertical Income Statements

Table 12: Comparison of common size Income statements

Comparison of common size Income statement	Revolut bank UAB	Commerzbank
Particulars	% of Net Operating Income	% of Net Operating Income
Interest income	38.41	163.20
Interest expense	-0.01	82.29
Net interest income	38.40	80.91
Fee and commission income	83.07	41.39
Fee and commission expense	-20.94	6.53
Net fee and commission income	62.13	34.86
Net operating income	100	100
Total operating expense	90.36	58.46
Total comprehensive profit or loss for the year, net of tax	7.54	23.06

- The common size income statement for Revolut Bank UAB and Commerzbank compares the composition of their income and expenses as a percentage of their respective net operating income. Here are some of the comparison's significant findings:
- Interest Income: Revolut Bank UAB earns 38.41% of its net operating income from interest income, but Commerzbank derives 163.20%, showing that interest income plays a larger role in Commerzbank's revenue.
- Interest Expense: Revolut Bank UAB has low-interest expenses, accounting for only -0.01% of net operating income, implying low borrowing costs or a unique financing arrangement.
- In comparison, Commerzbank's interest expenses are enormous, accounting for 82.29% of net operating income, showing a heavy reliance on borrowed money.
- Net Interest Income: Revolut Bank UAB's net interest income accounted for 38.40% of its net operating income, indicating a strong reliance on interest-related activities.

- Commerzbank's net interest revenue accounts for 80.91% of its net operating income, demonstrating a substantial reliance on interest income to produce profits.
- Fee and Commission Income: Fee and commission income accounts for 83.07% of Revolut Bank UAB's net operating income.
- Fees and commissions also contribute significantly to Commerzbank's revenue but at a lower percentage of 41.39%.
- Fees and commission expenses:
 - Revolut Bank UAB incurs a fee and commission expenditure equal to -20.94% of its net operating income, implying that fee waivers or discounts are in effect.
- The fee and commission expense at Commerzbank is relatively modest, accounting for 6.53% of net operating income.
- Net Fee and Commission Income: The net fee and commission income of Revolut Bank UAB is 62.13% of its net operating income, demonstrating a great performance in this area.
- Commerzbank's net fee and commission income accounts for 34.86% of its net operating income, demonstrating the bank's reliance on other sources of income.
- Total operating costs: Total operational expenses at Revolut Bank UAB account for 90.36% of net operating income, showing an incredibly high-cost structure
- Total operational expenses of Commerzbank are lower at 58.46% of net operating income, indicating greater cost management.
- Revolut Bank UAB reports a total comprehensive profit of 7.54% of its net operating income.
- The total comprehensive profit of Commerzbank is greater at 23.06% of net operating income, showing stronger overall profitability.
- In conclusion, the comparative common size income statement demonstrates that Revolut Bank UAB is primarily reliant on fee and commission income and has smaller interest-related income and expenses. In contrast, Commerzbank obtains a major amount of its revenue from interest income while maintaining excellent cost management. Commerzbank also reports a larger overall profit than Revolut Bank UAB.

4.4.2. Comparative Analysis of Vertical Balance Sheets:

Table 13: Balance Sheet

Balance Sheet	Revolut Bank UAB	Commerzbank
Assets	% of Total Assets	% of Total Assets
Cash on hand and cash on demand	73.00	16.94

Overdrafts (Revolut) / Amortised cost financial assets (Commerzbank)	4.03	59.79
Total assets	100.00	100.00
Due to customers (Revolut)/ Financial liabilities- Amortised cost and Financial Liabilities-Fair value options	94.26	88.39
Liabilities	95.34	93.63
Equity	4.65	6.37

- Revolut Bank UAB has a considerable quantity of cash and central bank balances, accounting for 73.00% of total assets.
- Commerzbank also has significant cash on hand and cash on demand, accounting for 16.94% of total assets.
- Revolut Bank UAB has a lower proportion of loans and overdrafts (4.03% of total assets).
- In comparison, Commerzbank has a larger portfolio of financial assets, with amortized cost financial assets accounting for 59.79% of total assets.
- Equity and liabilities:
 - Customers account for a sizable portion of Revolut Bank UAB's liabilities (94.26%).
 - Commerzbank likewise relies heavily on financial obligations in the form of amortized cost and fair value options (80.73% of total liabilities).
 - Revolut Bank UAB has 4.65% total equity as a percentage of total liabilities and equity. Commerzbank holds more equity, accounting for 6.37% of total liabilities and equity.
- It is vital to highlight that the two banks' business models differ, as seen by their financial statements. Revolut Bank UAB focuses on fees and commissions, whereas Commerzbank focuses on typical banking activities such as interest income. Furthermore, their balance sheets differ, with Revolut Bank holding a bigger proportion of its assets in cash and Commerzbank holding a larger portfolio of financial assets. Commerzbank likewise has a greater equity-to-liabilities ratio than Revolut.

4.5. Discussion

Revolut Ltd. started as an international money transferor at a lower price than most of the financial institutions were offering, it started with the help of an app and had bigger plans from the start. These bigger plans allowed it to partially become a registered online bank from Dec 2018 onwards; later Dec 2021, it was fully registered as Revolut Bank UAB. One of the reasons behind its registration

may be its growing customers, which reached 10 million by the year-end 2019, but the main reason which is very clear is that the Bank of Lithuania had a welcome regulatory authority for innovations as a result most of the fintech projects got registered in Lithuania in the shortest period, Revolut Ltd was one of among them. After getting fully registered Revolut Payment UAB was merged into Revolut Bank UAB and its customers were also linked to the Bank.

Revolut Bank UAB operates online through web-app chat or mobile app, because of which it has registered branches in the EU but they are not operational. The bank has a growing trend of growth in customers from 100000 in 2016 to 3000000 by the end of June 2023. This increase in several customers is unexpected and the competitors whose data is collected don't have growth up to such a large extent. It shows growth in Income is a little fluctuating as in the year 2021 its income was Euro 43.254 million declined to Euro 23970 and then again increased a little within 6 months to Euro 27million. Monzo Bank, one of the challenger banks was earning losses during the first two years, which showed diminishing losses but Commerzbank, one of the challenger banks also showed an increase in profit and again declined in the first half of 2023.

Again, comparing their analysis of financial statements, suggests that Commerzbank's income is higher than the rest of the banks highlighting secured investment for investors as it is one of the historical banks with positive earnings for many decades though their income shows little fluctuation, but in case of Revolut Bank UAB the income highlights a great decrease and then a small increase in next half, it means no consistency. On the other side, Monzo Bank shows continuous loss but its loss rate is decreasing.

The comparison of total assets shows an increasing trend in all three banks but the increase in Revolut Bank UAB is more than the rest of them, but in the case of equity all of them have consistency in growth. The reserves in the case of challenger banks are very clear to understand but in the case of Commerzbank there is a need to manage them properly as there are many reserves, but its only in the case of Revolut that it is using reserves to finance its cost for which the bank should look at some other alternatives.

The liquid cash with Revolut is increasing mostly twice in the second year and then nearly 9.5 % in the next year, this shows safety for investors, but consistency in liquid cash will give more surety for investors and customers to create deposits in this bank. Monzo Bank's cash balance is growing at a very slow rate. Further, Commerzbank has a cash balance at a consistent rate but along with it, this

bank also has other financial assets in traditional form, which are more secure than any other investments.

Revolut Bank UAB's profitability ratios ROE and ROA are declining, while in the case of Commerzbank, it increases and again decreases but at a very lower rate and Monzo Bank's ROE and ROA both are in minus at a diminishing rate, showing improvement. Revolut improvement in income is necessary to boost these ratios which shows the profitability of banks to investors and customers triggering to increase in faith among them and escalating more deposits and investments. An escalating trend highlights the good position of a Bank, instead of a dropping or fluctuating profitability trend.

Revolut Bank UABs' commission and fee income is more than interest income as a proportion of its operating Income on the other hand Commerzbank's Interest income is just more than double of operating profit and commission income is near its operating income, indicating a good amount of income from these two sources.

Revolut is in its growing stage, but it has lots of improvement every year, resulting in to increase in customers, which is not at all an easy part for a bank.

5. Conclusion:

Concluding the above and looking at the current trend of the world becoming more techno-oriented it is important to note that even the existing traditional banks are providing most of the facilities to their customers and investors at their fingertips by making it to be digitalized. As above, Commerzbank, which is very old historically is also shutting down a few branches every year and moving more to digitalization and renovation of other existing branches. It means slowly and gradually these fintech banks are going to occupy the whole market, out of which one of the leading fintech banks is Revolut Bank UAB.

5.1. Synopsis

The more detailed conclusion, based on Research questions are as follows:

RQ1. What is the foundation of Revolut Ltd Establishment as Revolut Bank UAB?

Revolut Bank UAB, formerly known as Revolut Ltd, was legally created on December 6, 2013, with company No. 8804411 and a registered office at 60 Arnhem Wharf, Arnhem Place, London, Great Britain, E143RU. However, according to several media articles and Lietuvos Banka statements, the bank was founded in the year 2015 and has been a source of controversy. While it was technically incorporated in 2013, it rose to prominence and regulatory recognition in the years that followed.

The following are major milestones in the growth of Revolut Bank UAB:

1. Change of Registered Office: The registered office was relocated to 1 Canada Square Level 39, 1 Canada Square, London E14 5AB on August 28, 2014.
2. Specialized Banking License (13th December 2018): On this day, the Bank of Lithuania issued Revolut Ltd a specialized banking license based on an evaluation and recommendation from Lithuania's financial regulatory authorities. With this license, Revolut Payments UAB was able to issue electronic money and provide a variety of payment services.
3. Full Banking License Upgrade (December 13, 2021): Revolut Bank UAB got a full banking license on December 13, 2021, officially becoming a Lithuanian bank with the registration number 304580906 and the authorization code LB002119. The official address was Konstitucijos Ave. 21B, 08130 Vilnius, Lithuania. This critical milestone allowed the bank to provide a greater variety of financial services and was regulated by the Bank of Lithuania as well as the European Central Bank.
4. Revolut Payment UAB Merger (1st July 2022): On July 1, 2022, Revolut Payment UAB merged with Revolut Bank UAB, and all customers of the former were integrated into the latter. This consolidation was an important milestone in the bank's development.
5. It is worth noting that Revolut Bank UAB's registration as a bank took some time, although the process was aided by the Bank of Lithuania's welcoming and innovation-friendly regulatory climate, which has one of the fastest licensing processes in the European Union. This was crucial in the founding and growth of the bank.

RQ2. What are the different types of measures to judge the growth of Revolut Bank UAB Ltd?

The different measurements will be in the form of the following:

1. **Different branches and Increase in the number of customers**
2. **SWOT analysis Of Revolut Bank UAB**
3. **Analysis of growth in customers, Income and branches as compared to Challenger banks Monzo Bank Ltd. and N26 as well as traditional bank, Commerzbank.**

1. Different branches and Increase in the number of customers

To summarize, Revolut Bank UAB has witnessed exceptional development in a relatively short period, owing mostly to its use of a digital-only, branchless strategy. The following are the important takeaways:

Branchless Model: Revolut Bank UAB has no physical branches. Instead, it provides its financial services completely through a mobile app and web-app chat, offering users with convenience and accessibility.

Customer Growth Has Been Explosive: The bank's growth has been nothing short of spectacular. It began with 100,000 customers in 2016, and within three years has grown to 10 million customers by 2019, representing a 100-fold increase. Following that, it swiftly expanded, reaching 14.5 million customers in 2020, 25 million in 2022, and a staggering 30 million by June 2023.

Consistent Growth: Following the massive rise from 2016 to 2019, Revolut Bank UAB has maintained stable and strong growth, adding between 4.5 million and 5 million users every year from 2019.

This quick expansion demonstrates the popularity of its digital banking services, innovative solutions, and capacity to adapt to changing client expectations. It shows the growing trend of digital-only banks, as well as their ability to attract and keep customers in a mobile and digital world.

2. SWOT analysis Of Revolut Bank UAB

Figure 3: SWOT analysis of Revolut Bank UAB

➤ Strengths:

- **Rapid Customer Growth:** A significant growth in customer numbers between 2016 and 2023, indicating an expanding user base.
- **Increasing Monthly Transactions:** A considerable increase in monthly transactions suggests increased consumer involvement.

- **Worldwide reach and Innovation:** Increasing worldwide reach while providing new financial products and services.
- **Tech-Driven Approach:** Using technology to fulfill modern client needs.
- **Funding Success:** Several significant investment rounds have contributed to the goal of becoming a worldwide financial super-app.
- **Financial Resilience:** Generating interest revenue consistently and keeping positive net interest income.

➤ **Weaknesses:**

- **Security Vulnerability:** A flaw in the payment system that can result in financial losses and security issues.
- **Payment System Error:** Payment system problems caused a large financial loss.

➤ **Opportunities:**

- **Tailored Consumer Finance:** Providing services that are tailored to specific market demands and preferences to provide a more personalized financial experience.
- **Expansion into Swiss Banking:** Pursuing a Swiss Representative Office license to expand into the Swiss market.

➤ **Threats:**

Vulnerabilities and risks related to data and financial loss are among the cybersecurity challenges. The banking sector is still vulnerable to cyberattacks and data breaches.

To summarize, Revolut Bank UAB has witnessed tremendous customer growth and innovation, which has been aided by significant funding. However, it is vulnerable to security flaws and cyber dangers, while the potential exists in specialized consumer finance and expansion into other countries, such as China.

3. **Analysis of growth in customers, Income and branches as compared to Challenger banks Monzo Bank Ltd. and N26 as well as traditional bank, Commerzbank.**

➤ **Growth in Customers:**

Figure 4: Growth in Customers (Sources: table 2)

From the above chart, it is clear that Revolut Bank UAB has exceptional and steady growth, beginning with 100,000 users in 2016 and reaching 30 million by June 2023. This growth vastly outpaces that of Monzo, which has been sluggish. While N26 had 2 million customers in the year 2018 and up to the year 2022 its total number of customers was only 8 million. On the other hand, Commerzbank's total number of customers was 18.5 million, which is again less than Revolut Bank UAB.

➤ **Income growth**

Figure 5: Income Growth (Sources: table3)

when comparing the growth in income of the banks from year 2021 to 2023:

- The net income of Revolut Bank UAB fluctuated but remained positive, growing from €43.254 million to €27.000 million.
- Monzo Bank's net loss fell from £-131.1 million in 2021 to £-119.0 million in 2022, and then to £-116.3 million in 2022, demonstrating a progressive improvement in the bank's financial status.
- N26's net loss increased 14.40%, from €-150.7 million to €-172.4 million.
- The net income of Commerzbank climbed dramatically from €354 million in 2021 to €1,393 million in 2022 before declining to €1,145 million in 2023.
- Revolut Bank UAB had a positive trend in net income in this environment, but the other banks either faced losses or lowered profitability.

➤ **Growth in Branch:**

These competitive banks have taken different approaches to their branch networks:

- Revolut Bank UAB is a completely digital bank with no physical branches.
- Monzo Bank is phasing its traditional branches to focus on expanding digital offerings.
- N26 is a digital-only bank that enables effective cost management.
- A conventional bank, Commerzbank, is closing physical locations and increasing digital links

RQ3. What is the final stage of analysis of comparative financial statements as on 31st December of 2021, 2022 and 30th June 2023?

➤ **Income Statement:**

Interest income and expenses fluctuated in all three banks (Revolut Bank UAB, Monzo Bank, and Commerzbank), with variable effects on net interest income.

In 2023, Monzo Bank had a net operating loss, while Revolut Bank UAB and Commerzbank improved their net operating income.

➤ **Balance Sheet:**

Revolut Bank UAB's total assets increased significantly from 2021 to 2022 and continued to grow considerably in 2023.

Total equity increased in all banks, albeit the rates of expansion varied.

➤ **Cash Flow Statement:**

From 2021 to 2023, Revolut Bank UAB's net cash flows from operating activities increased significantly.

In 2022, Monzo Bank experienced a negative net cash flow from operating activities, which may need to be addressed.

Net cash flows from operating activities improved at Commerzbank.

➤ **Statement of Equity Changes:**

Revolut Bank UAB had significant growth in equity components, particularly reserve capital.

Monzo Bank's other reserves increased significantly.

Commerzbank reported an increase in shareholder equity and capital components.

➤ **Profitability Ratios:**

➤

Figure 6: ROE (Sources Appendix 3)

Figure 7: ROA (Sources Appendix 3)

From the above Figures of ROE and ROA, there is clear indication that both the ROE and the ROA of Revolut Bank UAB are falling. Monzo Bank's poor ROE and ROA posed new hurdles. Commerzbank's ROE and ROA showed consistent but moderate improvements. Each bank may require specific attention to challenges influencing its profitability and efficiency.

Concluding above based on financial performance, Revolut Bank UAB's financial performance is showing improvement though initially it highlights a big drop and then a slow improvement in Income. The Cash balance, total assets and equity also show high improvement and then increase at a slower rate. However, the profitability ratios show declining trends indicating the need for an increase in comprehensive Income. Monzo Bank's financial performance is not good but there is improvement in loss at a reducing rate and improvement in total assets as well as Equity. Further, it also shows improvement in Profitability ratios by a decline in a negative trend. On the other hand, Commerzbank is the highest Income earner with a high increase in Income initially and then a decline at a slower rate, but its growth in equity is mostly at a consistent rate and a high increase in total assets in the final year. Cash flow also shows a great jump. However, the profitability ratios (ROE and ROA) highlight good growth initially and then decline at a very low rate.

RQ 4. What is the analysis of vertical financial statements of Revolut bank UAB as well as competitors Monzo Bank Ltd, N26 and Commerzbank as on 30th June 2023 indicates regarding the following:

- 1. Proportion of different income and expenses as compared to their Net operating Income and do Revolut Bank UAB have adequate Income to pay operating expenses? what does the analysis with competitor states?**
- 2. Proportion of different assets and liabilities as compared to their Total Assets and to measure the adequacy of assets to ensure financial security to customers, and investors, which is further preceded by comparison of Revolut Bank UAB with its competitors.**

In comparison to Revolut Bank UAB (38.41%), Commerzbank generates much larger interest income (163.20%). This means that Revolut may look for other ways to improve its interest income, such as diversifying its loan or investment activities.

Charges and Commissions Expenses and income: Revolut Bank UAB earns a significant amount of its revenue from fee and commission activities (83.07%), which is significantly greater than Commerzbank (41.39%). This is Revolut's area of strength, and they should continue to focus on increasing their fee and commission income streams.

Operating Expenses: Revolut Bank UAB's total operating expenses account for a bigger proportion of its net operating income (90.36%) than Commerzbank (58.46%). This suggests that Revolut should focus on cost management to minimize expenses and increase profitability. Possible cost-cutting measures include streamlining processes, renegotiating contracts, and investigating technology options for efficiency.

Total Comprehensive Profit or Loss: Commerzbank has a larger total comprehensive profit (23.06%) for the year than Revolut Bank UAB (7.54%). Revolut must increase its total profitability. To accomplish this, it should focus on generating revenue (such as interest and fee and commission income) while also managing costs more effectively.

Fee and commission expenses at Revolut Bank UAB are much greater as a percentage of net operating income (-20.94%) than at Commerzbank (6.53%). Revolut could think about lowering these costs by improving charge structures or enhancing the efficiency of fee-generating processes.

Finally, Commerzbank has greater overall profitability and a more balanced income mix, whereas Revolut Bank UAB excels in fee and commission income but has larger expenses. Revolut should examine the following techniques to increase its performance:

Diversify its revenue streams to include additional interest income.

Increasing efficiency and cost-cutting measures to reduce operating expenses.

Increasing its fee and commission income while keeping expenses to a minimum.

It's worth noting that the particular modifications Revolut Bank UAB should implement will be determined by its strategic goals and market conditions.

5.2. Research Limitations

This study's limitations originate from its reliance on data acquired from media and legal sources to follow the founding and growth of banks. Conclusions on the growth of banks are based on the sources employed to measure the growth of businesses like Revolut Bank UAB, especially if the competitive landscape changes.

Comparative financial statement analysis provides vital insights into assessing banks' financial health and making critical decisions for the near future. This utility, however, is restricted by the always-changing competitive environment, which is defined by the perpetual appearance of new competitors and altering conditions that demand ongoing strategy adjustments and decision modifications to assure profitability. It is critical to know that changes in the competitive landscape can result in a variety of outcomes that must be managed accordingly.

The comparison between common-size financial statement analysis is only between two banks. Therefore, further comparison with more competitors may change the decision.

5.3. Recommendations for future research

The research can be further done with a comparison between different competitors' financial statements, which may result to different decisions. Further collection of data on growth will bring different measurements and then growth can be judged accordingly.

Further, add up in more data in upcoming years may bring out some different results for comparative statements in the form of horizontal and vertical according to the performance of the banks.

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LIETUVOS BANKAS
LIETUVOS RESPUBLIKOS CENTRINIS BANKAS

LICENCIJA

Banking licence No. 22 Date 2021-12-13

Company Information		Decision maker	
Title	Revolut Bank UAB	Decision maker	European Central Bank
Company code	304580906		

Activity	Date	Decision No.	Issuer
Issuing of electronic money	2021-12-13	LIC-2020-0032 - ECB-SSM-2021-LT-7	European Central Bank
Services enabling cash to be placed on a payment account as well as all the operations required for operating a payment account	2021-12-13	LIC-2020-0032 - ECB-SSM-2021-LT-7	European Central Bank
Services enabling cash withdrawals from a payment account as well as all the operations required for operating a payment account	2021-12-13	LIC-2020-0032 - ECB-SSM-2021-LT-7	European Central Bank
Execution of payment transactions, including transfers of funds on a payment account with the payment service provider of the payment service user or with another payment service provider; execution of direct debits, including one-off direct debits, execution of payment transactions through a payment card or a	2021-12-13	LIC-2020-0032 - ECB-SSM-2021-LT-7	European Central Bank

1.A

execution of direct debits, including one-off direct debits, execution of payment transactions through a payment card or a similar device and/or execution of credit transfers, including standing orders	2021-12-13	LIC-2020-0032 - ECB-SSM-2021-LT-7	Central Bank
Receipt of deposits and other repayable funds from non-professional participants of the market	2021-12-13	LIC-2020-0032 - ECB-SSM-2021-LT-7	European Central Bank
Issuing of payment instruments and/or acquiring of payment;	2021-12-13	LIC-2020-0032 - ECB-SSM-2021-LT-7	European Central Bank
Money remittance	2021-12-13	LIC-2020-0032 - ECB-SSM-2021-LT-7	European Central Bank
payment initiation services	2021-12-13	LIC-2020-0032 - ECB-SSM-2021-LT-7	European Central Bank
account information services	2021-12-13	LIC-2020-0032 - ECB-SSM-2021-LT-7	European Central Bank
Execution of payment transactions where the funds are covered by a credit line for a payment service user; execution of direct debits, including one-off direct debits, execution of payment transactions through a payment card or a similar device and/or execution of credit transfers, including standing orders	2021-12-13	LIC-2020-0032 - ECB-SSM-2021-LT-7	European Central Bank

VILNIUS

Appendix 1B: Grant of specialised licenses

Revolut granted specialised bank and electronic money institution licences

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2018-12-13

Following the assessment and proposal of Lithuania's financial regulator, Revolut Technologies UAB has been granted a specialised bank licence by the European Central Bank, while the Board of the Bank of Lithuania issued Revolut Payments UAB an electronic money institution licence. The two companies are part of Revolut Ltd.

"Development of an environment conducive to competition and innovation in the field of finance is one of our strategic goals. We aim to ensure that Lithuania's financial sector provides quality services for consumers as well as creates a favourable ecosystem for business development," said Marius Jurgilas, Member of the Board of the Bank of Lithuania.

1 of 1

Having secured a specialised bank licence, Revolut Technologies UAB plans to accept deposits and offer consumer credits. The main difference between a specialised and a full-range bank is that the former is not authorised to provide investment services.

Revolut Payments UAB intends to issue electronic money and provide a wide range of payment services, such as payment transactions (card payments, direct debits, credit transfers), cash withdrawal, money remittance, payment initiation and account information services.

Revolut Ltd – the London-based startup – was founded in 2015. Its main scope of activities includes online transfers, currency exchange, card payments and cash withdrawal across the globe.

The Lithuanian FinTech cluster now includes more than 100 licensed companies, the majority of which are engaged in activities related to payments, electronic money issuance as well as P2P lending and crowdfunding platforms.

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Banking licence granted to Revolut Bank UAB

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2021-12-16

Following the proposal of the Bank of Lithuania, a specialised bank licence of Revolut Technologies UAB has been changed to a banking licence by the European Central Bank.

After extending and supplementing the licence, Revolut Bank UAB will complement its current main activities (accepting deposits and granting loans) with the payment services (card payments, direct debit, credit transfer, cash withdrawal, money remittance, payment initiation, account information services). These services are currently provided by Revolut Payments UAB, an electronic money institution of Revolut group licensed in Lithuania. The permission to reorganise it by way of merger with Revolut Bank UAB was granted by the Bank of Lithuania at the beginning of October this year.

1 of 1

As of the end of [Q3 2021](#), Revolut Bank UAB has received resident deposits of €395 million and provided almost €12 million in loans to residents.

In recent years, Revolut Payments UAB has carried out [payment transactions](#) for €100 billion, received nearly €170 million in operating income, and according to this indicator it occupies more than 50% of electronic money and payment institutions market in Lithuania.

[Both companies were granted licences in December 2018](#)

[Supervision of financial market participants](#), [Banks](#), [Payment institutions](#), [Electronic money institutions](#)

FinTech licensing boom: FinTech businesses discover the world of opportunities in Lithuania

Home / Media / News

2017-07-03

Having kick-started its ambitious goal of becoming a FinTech hub in the Nordic-Baltic region, Lithuania has already caught the attention of several dozen companies wishing to acquire a financial institution licence in the country. Since 2016, more than 20 companies have been granted authorisation, with quite a few more applications currently under review.

'It seems that the global FinTech sector has heard our message loud and clear: with the Bank of Lithuania acting as an accessible regulator, maintaining an open attitude towards innovation and ensuring one of the fastest licensing regimes in the EU, Lithuania is a perfect place to start and grow an international FinTech business.

As a result, the interest of both foreign and local companies has peaked', said Marius Jurgilas, Member of the Board of the Bank of Lithuania.

In the first half of 2017 alone, FinTech companies were granted 13 operating licences, which is already more than last year's total. Another dozen companies have submitted applications, meetings with numerous interested parties are taking place.

Mr Jurgilas believes that close cooperation between public authorities responsible for development in the domestic financial sector as well as the country's visibility in the global arena promoted by private partners (such as law firms, business accelerators, etc.) are among the key factors behind Lithuania's success.

According to Mr Jurgilas, foreign companies are particularly interested in obtaining a specialised bank, electronic money or payment institution licence that would grant the right to operate across the EU. This is especially true for companies in the post-Brexit UK: some of

BSS Newsletter Print

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Bank of Lithuania strengthens partnership with the National Bank of Moldova

2023 03 21

Supervision of financial market participants

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**CERTIFICATE OF INCORPORATION
OF A
PRIVATE LIMITED COMPANY**

Company No. 8804411

The Registrar of Companies for England and Wales, hereby certifies that

REVOLUT LTD

is this day incorporated under the Companies Act 2006 as a private company, that the company is limited by shares, and the situation of its registered office is in England and Wales

Given at Companies House, Cardiff, on 6th December 2013

N08804411D

The above information was communicated by electronic means and authenticated by the Registrar of Companies under section 1115 of the Companies Act 2006

Companies House

Appendix 2.B: Registration of a charge

Companies House

MR01 (ef)

Registration of a Charge

Company name: **REVOLUT LTD**
Company number: **08804411**

Received for Electronic Filing: **23/04/2018**

Details of Charge

Date of creation: **16/04/2018**
Charge code: **0880 4411 0003**
Persons entitled: **TRIPLEPOINT VENTURE GROWTH BDC CORP.**
Brief description: **REGISTERED TRADE MARKS WITH REGISTRATION NUMBERS 3098083 AND 3286723. REGISTERED PATENT WITH APPLICATION NUMBER 14/549,837. PLEASE SEE INSTRUMENT FOR FURTHER DETAILS.**
Contains fixed charge(s).
Contains floating charge(s) (floating charge covers all the property or undertaking of the company).
Contains negative pledge.

Authentication of Form

This form was authorised by: **a person with an interest in the registration of the charge.**

Authentication of Instrument

Certification statement: **I CERTIFY THAT SAVE FOR MATERIAL REDACTED PURSUANT TO S. 859G OF THE COMPANIES ACT 2006 THE ELECTRONIC**

Companies House

AD01 (ef)

Change of Registered Office Address

Company Name: **REVOLUT LTD**

Company Number: **08804411**

Received for filing in Electronic Format on the: **27/08/2014**

03/4/LEP

New Address Details

New Address: **1 CANADA SQUARE LEVEL 39. 1 CANADA SQUARE
LONDON
ENGLAND
E14 5AB**

Please Note:

The change in the Registered Office does not take effect until the Registrar has registered this form. For 14 days, beginning with the date that a change of Registered Office is registered, a person may validly serve any documentation on the company at its previous Registered Office.

Authorisation

Authenticated

This form was authorised by one of the following:

Director, Secretary, Person Authorised, Liquidator, Administrator, Administrative Receiver, Receiver, Receiver Manager, Charity Commission Receiver and Manager, CIC Manager, Judicial Factor.

Appendix 3 A: Profitability Ratios (ROE and ROA)

Profitability ratios

ROE	2021	2022	2023
Revolut Bank UAB	17.10	6.04	5.59
Monzo Bank	-59.07	-21.17	-
Commerzbank	1.44	4.64	3.64

ROA	2021	2022	2023
Revolut Bank UAB	0.89	0.27	0.26
Monzo Bank	-3.61	-2.28	-
Commerzbank	0.09	0.30	0.23

Appendix 3 B: Common size financial statements

Revolut Bank UAB			
Consolidated statement of comprehensive income			
Common size Income statement			
€'000	Jun-23	Column1	
	Euro	% of Net Op. In	
Interest Income calculated using the effective interest method	137490	38.41	
Interest expenses	-31	-0.01	
Net interest income	137459	38.40	
Fees and commission income	297338	83.07	
Fees and commission expenses	-74952	-20.94	
Net fee and commission income	222386	62.13	
Net gains and losses on financial items	28438	7.95	
Credit loss expense on financial assets	-21794	-6.09	
Exchange difference gain (loss)	-8503	-2.38	
Provisions	-54	-0.02	
other operating income	0	0.00	
Net operating income	357932	100.00	
Personnel expenses	21750	6.08	
depreciation and amortisation	181	0.05	
other operating expenses	301497	84.23	
Total operating expenses	323428	90.36	
Profit before tax	34504	9.64	
Tax expenses	7504	2.10	
Profit for the year	27000	7.54	
Net change in fair value of debt instruments at FVOCI	0	0.00	
Foreign currency translation	0	0.00	
Other comprehensive income for the year	0	0.00	
Total comprehensive income for the year, net of tax	27000	7.54	

Revolut Bank UAB			
Consolidated statement of financial position			
Comparative statement financial position			
	Jun-23		
	Euro		
Column1	Column2	Column3	
Assets	Euro	% of Total Assets	
Cash and balances with central banks	75,77,198	73.00	
Due from banks	11,658	0.11	
Due from other financial institutions		0.00	
Debt securities/ Debt instruments at amortised cost	1854403	17.87	
Equity instruments	25	0.00	
Loans and unauthorised overdrafts	4,18,776	4.03	
Due from intermediaries		0.00	
Derivatives	2691	0.03	
Property and equipment and right of use assets	1348	0.01	
Intangible assets	0	0.00	
Deferred tax assets	0	0.00	
Other assets	513818	4.95	
Total assets	1,03,79,917	100.00	
Liabilities		0.00	
Derivatives	194	0.00	
Due to customers	9783673	94.26	
lease liabilities	1366	0.01	
Due to other financial institutions	0	0.00	
other liabilities	111204	1.07	
Provisions	161	0.00	
Total liabilities	9896598	95.34	
Equity attributable to equity holders of parent		0.00	
Share capital	36,815	0.35	
Reserve capital	0	0.00	
Retained earnings	98,317	0.95	
Other reserves	3,47,887	3.35	
Total equity	4,83,019	4.65	
Total liabilities and equity	1,03,79,617	100.00	

common size Income statement			
Comparative Income Statement			
	Column1	Change dec2021-2022	
	Jun-23	% of Net Op. In	
Interest income	8222	163.20	
Interest expenses	4146	82.29	
Net interest income	4076	80.91	
Dividend income	3	0.06	
Risk result	-276	-5.48	
Commission income	2085	41.39	
Commission expenses	329	6.53	
Net commission income	1756	34.86	
Net income from hedge accounting	7	0.14	
Gain or loss from financial assets and liabilities measured	-90	-1.79	
Other profit or loss from financial instruments, income fr	-16	-0.32	
Gain or loss on disposal of financial assets – Amortised co	34	0.67	
Current net income from companies accounted for using	3	0.06	
other net income	-477	-9.47	
other net income from financial instruments	18	0.36	
Net operating income	5038	100.00	
operating expenses	2945	58.46	
compulsory contributions	312	6.19	
Restructuring expenses	8	0.16	
Pre-tax profit or loss	1773	35.19	
Taxes on income	617	12.25	
Consolidated profit/loss	1156	22.95	
Consolidated profit or loss attributable to non-controlling	-6	-0.12	
Consolidated profit or loss attributable to Commerzban	1162	23.06	

€m			
Consolidated Balance sheet			
	Jun-23	% of Total Assets	
Financial assets – Amortised cost	37245	7.43	
Financial assets – Fair value OCI	41235	8.22	
Financial assets – Mandatorily fair value P&L	30750	6.13	
Financial assets – Held for trading	92457	18.43	
Other assets	501602	100.00	
Total		0.00	
	404919	80.73	
Financial liabilities- Amortised cost	38460	7.67	
Financial Liabilities-Fair value options	18737	3.74	
Financial Liabilities- Held for trading	7542	1.50	
Other Liabilities	31944	6.37	
Equity	501602	100.00	
Total		0.00	

Commerzbank			
Balance Sheet			
Assets	Jun-23	% of Total Assets	Column1
Cash on hand and cash on demand	84959	16.94	
Financial assets – Amortised cost	299915	59.79	
of which pledged as collateral	2597	0.52	
Financial assets – Fair value OCI	37245	7.43	
of which pledged as collateral	7622	1.52	
Financial assets – Mandatorily fair value P&L	41235	8.22	
of which pledged as collateral	0	0.00	
Financial assets – Held for trading	30750	6.13	
of which pledged as collateral	2560	0.51	
Value adjustment on portfolio fair value hedges	-3666	-0.73	
Positive fair values of derivative hedging instruments	1706	0.34	
Holdings in companies accounted for using the equity method	163	0.03	
Intangible assets	1352	0.27	
Fixed assets	2314	0.46	
Investment properties	59	0.01	
Non-current assets held for sale and disposal groups			
	139	0.03	
Current tax assets	167	0.03	
Deferred tax assets	2725	0.54	
Other assets	2539	0.51	
Total	501602	100.00	
Liabilities and equity/€m		0.00	
Financial liabilities- Amortised cost	404919	80.73	
Financial Liabilities- Fair value options	38460	7.67	
Financial Liabilities- Held for trading	18737	3.74	
Value adjustment on portfolio fair value hedges	-4339	-0.87	
Negative fair values of derivative hedging instruments	3494	0.70	
Provisions	3358	0.67	
Current tax liabilities	640	0.13	
Deferred tax liabilities	5	0.00	
Liabilities of disposal groups	0	0.00	
Other liabilities	4384	0.87	
Equity	31944	6.37	
Subscribed capital	1240	0.25	
Capital reserve	10075	2.01	
Retained earnings	17209	3.43	
Other reserves (with recycling)	-668	-0.13	
Equity attributable to Commerzbank shareholders	27856	5.55	
Additional equity components	3114	0.62	
Non-controlling interests	974	0.19	
Total	501602	100.00	

Appendix 3 C: Revolut Bank UAB Comparative financial statements

Revolut Bank UAB							
Consolidated statement of comprehensive income							
Comparative Income statement	Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5	Column6	Column7
Particulars	Dec-21	Dec-22	Jun-23	Change dec2021-2022		Change Dec 2022-June 2023	
	Euro (000)	Euro (000)	Euro (000)	Euro (000)	%	Euro (000)	%
Interest Income calculated using the effective interest	1298	40386	137490	39088.00	3011.40	97104	240.44
Interest expenses	-13823	-12519	-31	1304.00	-9.43	12488	-99.75
Net interest income	-12525	27,867	137459	40392.00	-322.49	109592	393.27
Fees and commission income	247631	4,43,442	297338	195811.00	79.07	-146104	-32.95
Fees and commission expenses	-97142	-113066	-74952	-15924.00	16.39	38114	-33.71
Net fee and commission income	150489	3,30,376	222386	179887.00	119.53	-107990	-32.69
Net gains and losses on financial items	-7246	6762	28438	14008.00	-193.32	21676	320.56
Credit loss expense on financial assets	-8199	-21569	-21794	-13370.00	163.07	-225	1.04
Exchange difference gain (loss)	0	0	-8503	0.00	#DIV/0!	-8503	#DIV/0!
Provisions	0	0	-54	0.00	#DIV/0!	-54	#DIV/0!
other operating income	14373	46211	0	31838.00	221.51	-46211	-100.00
Net operating income	136892	3,89,647	357932	252755.00	184.64	-31715	-8.14
Personnel expenses	-6447	-22525	21750	-16078.00	249.39	44275	-196.56
depreciation and amortisation	-213	-373	181	-160.00	75.12	554	-148.53
other operating expenses	-77226	-336582	301497	-259356.00	335.84	638079	-189.58
Total operating expenses	-83886	-359480	323428	-275594.00	328.53	682908	-189.97
Profit before tax	53006	30,167	34504	-22839.00	-43.09	4337	14.38
Tax expenses	-9357	-6612	7504	2745.00	-29.34	14116	-213.49
Profit for the year	43649	23,555	27000	-20094.00	-46.04	3445	14.63
Net change in fair value of debt instruments at FVOCI	-400	400	0	800.00	-200.00	-400	-100.00
Foreign currency translation	5	15	0	10.00	200.00	-15	-100.00
Other comprehensive income for the year	-395	415	0	810.00	-205.06	-415	-100.00
Total comprehensive income for the year, net of tax	43254	23,970	27000	-19284.00	-44.58	3030	12.64

Revolut Bank UAB							
Consolidated statement of financial position							
Comparative statement financial position	Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5	Column6	Column7
Particulars	Dec-21	Dec-22	Jun-23	Change dec2021-2022		Change Dec 2022-June 2023	
	Euro (000)	Euro (000)	Euro (000)	Euro (000)	%	Euro (000)	%
Assets							
Cash and balances with central banks	3448265	6921501	75,77,198	3473236.00	100.72	6,55,697	9.47
Due from banks	115091	8396	11,658	-106695.00	-92.70	3,262	38.85
Due from other financial institutions	129484	1358		-128126.00	-98.95	-1,358	-100.00
Debt securities/ Debt instruments at amortised cost	1015081	1110256	1854403	95175.00	9.38	7,44,147	67.02
Equity instruments	25	25	25	0.00	0.00	0	0.00
Loans and unauthorised overdrafts	23548	230837	4,18,776	207289.00	880.28	1,87,939	81.42
Due from intermediaries	15716	13135		-2581.00	-16.42	-13,135	-100.00
Derivatives	4737	1261	2691	-3476.00	-73.38	1,430	113.40
Property and equipment and right of use assets	1701	1447	1348	-254.00	-14.93	-99	-6.84
Intangible assets	33	0	0	-33.00	-100.00	0	#DIV/0!
Deferred tax assets	1547	4660	0	3113.00	201.23	-4,660	-100.00
Other assets	123169	486599	513818	363430.00	295.07	27,219	5.59
Total assets	4878397	8779475	1,03,79,917	3901078.00	79.97	16,00,442	18.23
Liabilities							
Derivatives	8284	2800	194	-5484.00	-66.20	-2,606	-93.07
Due to customers	4544087	8083838	9783673	3539751.00	77.90	16,99,835	21.03
lease liabilities	0	0	1366	0.00	#DIV/0!	1,366	#DIV/0!
Due to other financial institutions	24155	191561	0	167406.00	693.05	-1,91,561	-100.00
other liabilities	48964	104416	111204	55452.00	113.25	6,788	6.50
Provisions	32	103	161	71.00	221.88	58	56.31
Total liabilities	4625522	8382718	9896598	3757196.00	81.23	15,13,880	18.06
Equity attributable to equity holders of parent							
Share capital	36815	36815	36,815	0.00	0.00	0	0.00
Reserve capital	169600	279008	0	109408.00	64.51	-2,79,008	-100.00
Retained earnings	44451	75071	98,317	30620.00	68.88	23,246	30.97
Other reserves	2009	5863	3,47,887	3854.00	191.84	3,42,024	5833.60
Total equity	252875	396757	4,83,019	143882.00	56.90	86,262	21.74
Total liabilities and equity	4878397	8779475	1,03,79,617	3901078.00	79.97	16,00,142	18.23

Comparative statement of Cash flow statement	Dec-21	Dec-22	Change dec	Column1
Particulars	Euro (000)	Euro (000)	Euro (000)	%
Operating Activities				
Profit before tax	53006	30167	-22839	-43.09
Adjustment for:			0	#DIV/0!
Interest income	-1298	-40386	-39088	3011.40
Interest expense	13823	12519	-1304	-9.43
Financial assets impairment	-7088	21625	28713	-405.09
Depreciation and amortisation	213	373	160	75.12
Changes in operating assets and liabilities			0	#DIV/0!
Net changes in derivative financial instruments	-253	-2008	-1755	693.68
Net changes in loans and unauthorised overdrafts	-20023	-227763	-207740	1037.51
Net change in financial assets	-1015506	-94877	920629	-90.66
Change in other operating assets	-52030	-360796	-308766	593.44
Change in other operating liabilities	35137	236364	201227	572.69
Increase in deposits	1754878	3539751	1784873	101.71
Gain(-)/loss (+) from exchange differences	4165	-37466	-41631	-999.54
Share based payments to employees	1243	912	-331	-26.63
Provision for deferred assets	-1085	-3113	-2028	186.91
Income tax paid	-1221	-19830	-18609	1524.08
Interest paid	-13855	-12579	1276	-9.21
Interest received	1221	39408	38187	3127.52
Net cash flows from operating activities	698321	3052134	2353813	337.07
Investing activities				
Purchase of property and equipment	-16	-18	-2	12.50
Net cash flows used in investing activities	-16	-18	-2	12.50
Financing activities				
Proceeds from formation of reserve capital	159600	119000	-40600	-25.44
Principal payments of lease liabilities	-168	-349	-181	107.74
Net cash flows from financing activities	159432	118651	-40781	-25.58
Net increase in cash and cash equivalents	910743	3200934	2290191	251.46
Net foreign exchange difference	-4160	37481	41641	-1000.99
Cash and cash equivalents at 1 January	2786257	3692840	906583	32.54
Cash and cash equivalents at 31 December	3692840	6931255	3238415	37.69

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1. In the absence of comparison is only

2. Further while prep comparison will be only for Income Stat is not provided in an

Appendix 3 E: Monzo Bank Comparative Financial Statements

Commerzbank								
All amounts are in euro million								
Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5	Column6	Column7	Column8	Column9
Comparative Income Statement				Change dec2021-2022		Change Dec 2022-June 2023		
	Dec-21	Dec-22	Jun-23	€	%	€	%	
Interest income	7268	10332	8222	3064	42.16	-2110	-20.42	
Interest expenses	2419	3873	4146	1454	60.11	273	7.05	
Net interest income	4849	6459	4076	1610	33.20	-2383	-36.89	
Dividend income	22	32	3	10	45.45	-29	-90.63	
Risk result	-570	-876	-276	-306	53.68	600	-68.49	
Commission income	4255	4194	2085	-61	-1.43	-2109	-50.29	
Commission expenses	648	675	329	27	4.17	-346	-51.26	
Net commission income	3607	3519	1756	-88	-2.44	-1763	-50.10	
Net income from hedge accounting			7	0	#DIV/0!	7	#DIV/0!	
Gain or loss from financial assets and liabilities measured at fair value	883	337	-90	-546	-61.83	-427	-126.71	
Other profit or loss from financial instruments, income and expenses	-911	-886	-16	25	-2.74	870	-98.19	
Gain or loss on disposal of financial assets – Amortised cost			34	0	#DIV/0!	34	#DIV/0!	
Current net income from companies accounted for using the equity method			3	0	#DIV/0!	3	#DIV/0!	
other net Income			-477	0	#DIV/0!	-477	#DIV/0!	
operating expenses	6230	5844	2945	-386	-6.20	-2899	-49.61	
other net income from financial instruments			18	0	#DIV/0!	18	#DIV/0!	
compulsory contributions	467	642	312	175	37.47	-330	-51.40	
Operating profit or loss	1183	2099	1781	916	77.43	-318	-15.15	
Restructuring expenses	1078	94	8	-984	-91.28	-86	-91.49	
Pre-tax profit or loss	105	2005	1773	1900	1809.52	-232	-11.57	
Taxes on income	-248	612	617	860	-346.77	5	0.82	
Consolidated profit/loss	353	1393	1156	1040	294.62	-237	-17.01	
Consolidated profit or loss attributable to non-controlling interests	-77	-42	-6	35	-45.45	36	-85.71	
Consolidated profit or loss attributable to Commerzbank	430	1435	1162	1005	233.72	-273	-19.02	

Change dec2021-2022								
Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5	Column6	Column7	Column8	Column9
Consolidated Balance sheet				€	%	€	%	
Financial assets – Amortised cost	299181	296192	299915	-2989	-1.00	3723	1.26	
Financial assets – Fair value OCI	40,115	34887	37245	-5228	-13.03	2358	6.76	
Financial assets – Mandatorily fair value P&L	28433	29913	41235	1480	5.21	11322	37.85	
Financial assets – Held for trading	38155	33573	30750	-4582	-12.01	-2823	-8.41	
Other assets	61525	82873	92457	21348	34.70	9584	11.56	
Total	467409	477438	501602	10029	2.15	24164	5.06	
Financial liabilities- Amortised cost	373976	390385	404919	16409	4.39	14534	3.72	
Financial Liabilities-Fair value options	19735	25018	38460	5283	26.77	13442	53.73	
Financial Liabilities- Held for trading	27322	24759	18737	-2563	-9.38	-6022	-24.32	
Other Liabilities	16549	6371	7542	-10178	-61.50	1171	18.38	
Equity	29827	30905	31944	1078	3.61	1039	3.36	
Total	467409	477438	501602	10029	2.15	24164	5.06	

Change dec2021-2022								
Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5	Column6	Column7	Column8	Column9
Cash flow statement				€	%	€	%	
Consolidated profit or loss	354	1393	1039	293.50				
Non-cash positions in consolidated profit or loss and reconciliation with cashflow from Change in other				#DIV/0!				
Write-downs, depreciation, write-ups on fixed and other intangible assets	6290	554	-5736	-91.19				
Net gain or loss on the sale of fixed assets	2825	-6015	-8840	-312.92				
Other adjustments	4	36	32	800.00				
Change in assets and liabilities from operating activities	-3239	-5062	-1823	56.28				
Sub Total	6234	-9094	-15328	-245.88				
Change in assets and liabilities from operating activities after adjustment for non-current assets and liabilities				#DIV/0!				
Financial assets - Amortised cost	-6818	2793	9611	-140.97				
Financial assets - Mandatorily fair value P&L	-213	-1338	-1125	528.17				
Financial assets – Fair value OCI	2746	5228	2482	90.39				
Financial assets - Held for trading	-6913	2793	9706	-140.40				
Other assets from operating activities	840	480	-360	-42.86				
Financial liabilities – Amortised cost	-22302	17756	40058	-179.62				
Financial liabilities – Fair value option	-940	3975	4915	-522.87				
Financial liabilities – Held for trading	0	7	7	#DIV/0!				
Other liabilities from operating activities	479	184	-295	-61.59				
Net cash from contributions into plan assets	-2254	-2570	-316	14.02				
Interest received	7663	9585	1922	25.08				
Dividends received	22	32	10	45.45				
Interest paid	-2477	-3739	-1262	50.95				
Income tax paid	-328	-233	95	-28.96				
Net cash from operating activities	-24261	25859	50120	-206.59				
Proceeds from the sale of:				#DIV/0!				
Holdings in subsidiaries and companies accounted for	-87	76	163	-187.36				
Fixed assets and intangible assets	278	55	-223	-80.22				
Payments for the acquisition of:				#DIV/0!				
Holdings in subsidiaries and companies accounted for	-24	-62	-38	158.33				
Fixed assets and intangible assets	-973	-675	298	-30.63				
Effects from changes in the group of consolidated companies				#DIV/0!				
Cash flow from acquisitions less cash reserves acquired	0	0	0	#DIV/0!				
Cash flow from disposals less cash reserves disposed of	2	-106	-108	-5400.00				
Net cash from investing activities	-804	-713	91	-11.32				
Dividend paid on shares previous year	0	0	0	#DIV/0!				
Raising/repayment of subordinated liabilities	-1375	477	1852	-134.69				
Additional equity components	495	0	-495	-100.00				
Repayment of lease liabilities	-331	-299	32	-9.67				
Net cash from financing activities	-1211	178	1389	-114.70				
Cash and cash equivalents at the end of the previous period	75603	49507	-26096	-34.52				
Net cash from operating activities	-24261	25859	50120	-206.59				
Net cash from investing activities	-804	-713	91	-11.32				
Net cash from financing activities	-1211	178	1389	-114.70				
Effects from exchange rate changes	180	402	222	123.33				
Cash and cash equivalents at the end of the period	49507	75233	25726	51.96				

Balance Sheet								
Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5	Column6	Column7	Column8	Column9
Assets				€	%	€	%	
Cash on hand and cash on demand	49507	75233	84959	25726	51.96	9726	12.93	
Financial assets – Amortised cost	299181	296192	299915	-2989	-1.00	3723	1.26	
of which pledged as collateral	873	3282	2597	2409	275.95	-685	-20.87	
Financial assets – Fair value OCI	40115	34887	37245	-5228	-13.03	2358	6.76	
of which pledged as collateral	3645	5335	7622	1690	46.36	2287	42.87	
Financial assets – Mandatorily fair value P&L	28432	29912	41235	1480	5.21	11322	37.85	
of which pledged as collateral	0	0	0	0	#DIV/0!	0	#DIV/0!	

Declaration of Authenticity

I hereby declare that I have completed the Master's thesis on my own and without any additional external assistance. I have made use of only those sources and aids specified and I have listed all the sources from which I have extracted text and content. This thesis or parts thereof have never been presented to another examination board. I agree to a plagiarism check of my thesis via a plagiarism detection service.

Berlin, 08/11/ 2023

Place, Date

Student Signature